

UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST OF SCOTLAND

DOCTORAL THESIS

**Machine learning Applications for
Medical Imaging**

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Declaration of Authorship

I, Gabriel Iluebe Okolo , declare that this thesis titled, “Machine learning Applications for Medical Imaging” and the work presented in it are my own. I confirm that:

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- Where I have consulted the published work of others, this is always clearly attributed.
- Where I have quoted from the work of others, the source is always given. With the exception of such quotations, this thesis is entirely my own work.
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Signed:

Date:

“I dedicate this thesis to God Almighty, I am most grateful to God for his mercies, favour and grace upon my life. I greatly forward my heart gratitude to my loving parents Prof. and Mrs. A. Okolo, without whom I would not have been here now. You are a great blessing to my life. May God in heaven reward you bountifully for the true love you both have shown me. A special feeling of gratitude to my brother and sisters for their continuous support, prayers and their words of encouragement.”

Gabriel Iluebe Okolo

Abstract

Huge amount of medical imaging data is produced everyday, due to the advancements in clinical diagnostic technology in hospitals and research facilities. It is also impossible for physicians and radiologists to analyse every image without making any subjective mistakes due to the volume, diversity, and pace of image formation. Radiologists can benefit from automatic disease diagnosis by having less work to do and providing better patient care. In order to help radiologists and doctors better use medical imaging data for automatic medical imaging diagnosis, this thesis presents original ideas and implements systems that makes it possible for computers to interpret medical imaging data in a way that clinicians can. In order to do this, it is anticipated that the findings of this thesis would enhance applications in a variety of medical image analysis disciplines, including medical classification, detection and localisation.

Recent advances in machine learning have made possible the automated diagnosis of diseases through computer aided diagnosis. This has led to the key contributions of this thesis which are summarized as follows: A multi-modal approach for lung ultrasound image classification that combines image-based features with information about the type of ultrasound probe. Experiments on a large lung ultrasound image dataset that contains images acquired with a linear or a convex ultrasound probe demonstrated the superiority of the proposed approach for the task of classifying lung ultrasound images as “COVID-19”, “Normal”, “Pneumonia”, or “Other”, when compared to simply using image-based features. Classification accuracy reached 99.98% using the proposed combination of the pre-trained CNN model with the ultrasound probe information, as opposed to 96.81% when only using the pre-trained CNN model.

A neural network architecture for the task of classifying chest X-ray images as belonging to healthy individuals, individuals with COVID-19 or individuals with viral pneumonia. The proposed technique attained a high classification accuracy of 98.04% and a highest F1-score of 98.22%.

An Input Enhanced Vision Transformer (IEViT), a novel enhanced Vision Transformer model that can achieve improved performance on chest X-ray images associated with various pathologies. Experiments on four chest X-ray image data sets containing various pathologies (tuberculosis, pneumonia, COVID-19) demonstrated that the proposed IEViT model outperformed ViT for all the data sets and variants examined, achieving an F1-score between 96.39% and 100%, and an improvement over ViT of up to +5.82% in terms of F1-score across the four examined data sets. IEViT’s maximum sensitivity (recall) ranged between 93.50% and 100% across the four data sets, with an improvement over ViT of up to +3%, whereas IEViT’s maximum precision ranged between 97.96% and 100% across the four data sets, with an improvement over ViT of up to +6.41%.

Finally, a CXR Localisation Network (CLN) framework, a multi-task deep neural network designed for CXR image localisation and classification. The proposed architecture was trained and evaluated on a subset of the ChestX-ray14 CXR data set, which included bounding box annotations of eight different pathologies from expert radiologists. The results demonstrated that the approach outperformed state-of-the-art methods in both CXR image localisation and classification, achieving a maximum classification mean AUC score of 0.893 and a maximum localisation mean IoU accuracy of 0.855.

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Contents

Declaration of Authorship	iii
Dedication	v
Abstract	vii
Acknowledgements	ix
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Motivation	1
1.2 Research Questions	2
1.3 Research Objectives	2
1.4 Summary of Contributions	2
1.5 Thesis Organisation	3
2 Background	5
2.1 Machine learning	5
2.1.1 Types of Machine learning	5
Supervised learning	5
Unsupervised learning	6
Reinforcement learning	6
2.1.2 Model Selection	6
2.1.3 Preprocessing data	7
Normalization of Data	7
Principal Component Analysis	7
Whitening	7
2.1.4 K-Nearest Neighbor Approach	7
2.1.5 Support Vector Machines Approach	7
2.1.6 Decision Trees and Extremely Randomized Trees	8
2.2 Deep learning	8
2.2.1 Deep Neural Network	8
Basic Concept	8
Multilayer Perceptron	9
Gradient Descent and Error Backpropagation	9
Avoid Overfitting- Regularization	10
2.2.2 Convolutional neural network	10
Convolutional layers	11
Pooling layers	11
Fully Connected Layer	12
Nonlinear Activation Function	12
Loss Function	12
2.3 Image classification	12
2.4 Optimization Techniques	13
2.4.1 Regularization technique	13
Regularization through data	13
Regularization through network architectures	13
2.5 Transfer Learning	14
2.5.1 Transfer learning with convolutional neural networks	14
2.6 Data Augmentation	15

3	Literature Review	17
3.1	Medical Imaging	17
3.1.1	Medical Imaging Modalities	17
3.2	Medical Imaging Research Issues and Discussions	18
3.2.1	Main Challenges for Medical Imaging	18
3.2.2	Directions for Medical Imaging	18
3.3	Machine Learning in Medical Imaging	19
3.4	Applications of Machine Learning for Computer Aided Diagnosis (CAD) in Medical Imaging	19
3.5	Chest X-ray Images	20
3.6	Deep Learning for Chest X-ray Images Classification and Detection	21
3.7	Deep Learning for Chest X-ray Images Localization	23
3.8	Lung ultrasound Images	24
3.9	Deep Learning for Lung Ultra Sound Images Classification and Detection	24
3.10	Metrics for Medical Imaging System Evaluation	25
3.11	Summary	25
4	Multi-modal lung ultrasound image classification by fusing image-based features and probe information	27
4.1	Research Methodology	27
4.1.1	Dataset	28
4.1.2	Proposed architecture	28
4.1.3	Training and classification	29
4.2	Results & Discussion	30
4.2.1	Experimental results	31
4.2.2	Comparison to state of the art	31
4.2.3	Additional Discussion	31
4.3	Summary	32
5	On the Use of Deep Learning for Imaging-based COVID-19 Detection Using Chest X-rays	35
5.1	Research Methodology	37
5.1.1	Data set	37
5.1.2	Application of data augmentation	38
5.1.3	Classification using deep neural networks	38
	Baseline approach	39
	Approach 1	39
	Approach 2	39
5.1.4	Hyperparameter settings and added layers	39
5.1.5	Label Smoothing	40
5.2	Results and Discussion	41
5.2.1	Results for the Baseline Approach	41
5.2.2	Results for Approach 1	41
5.2.3	Results for Approach 2	42
5.2.4	Validation on unseen data set	42
5.2.5	Execution time	43
5.2.6	Discussion	43
5.3	Summary	46
6	IEViT: An Input Enhanced Vision Transformer Architecture for Chest X-ray Image Classification	49
6.1	Research Methodology	50
6.1.1	Data set	50
6.1.2	The original Vision Transformer (ViT) architecture	51
6.1.3	The proposed Input Enhanced Vision Transformer (IEViT)	52
6.1.4	Training and Classification	53
6.2	Results	54
6.2.1	Classification experiments	54

6.2.2	Classification results per data set	55
6.2.3	Ablation study	58
6.2.4	Comparison to established CNN models	58
6.3	Discussion	59
6.4	Summary	61
7	CLN: A multi-task deep neural network for chest X-ray image localisation and classification	63
7.1	Research Methodology	63
7.1.1	CXR data set	63
7.1.2	Image feature extraction backbone	64
7.1.3	CXR image classification module	65
7.1.4	CXR image localisation module	65
7.1.5	Loss function & Training	65
7.2	Experimental Results	66
7.2.1	Evaluation Protocol & Metrics	66
7.2.2	Pathology Localisation	66
7.2.3	Pathology Classification	67
7.2.4	Ablation study	69
7.2.5	Further Discussion	70
7.3	Summary	71
8	Conclusions & Future Work	73
8.1	Conclusions	73
8.2	Future Work	74
	Bibliography	75

List of Figures

2.1	Illustration of a single neuron with four input values x_1, x_2, x_3, b .	9
2.2	Example of a multilayer perceptron.	9
2.3	Convolutional neural network.	10
2.4	Convolutional Operation.	11
2.5	Max Pooling Operation 2.	11
2.6	Dropout and DropConnect with dropout probability at 0.5.	14
2.7	Transfer Learning Process.	14
2.8	Four Transfer Learning Approaches.	15
2.9	Data Augmentation Process.	15
3.1	Chest X-ray images.	17
3.2	Ultrasound images.	18
4.1	Example US images from the COVIDx-US dataset for each class and probe type. (a-d) linear probe, (e-h) convex probe.	28
4.2	Outline of the proposed architecture.	29
4.3	Confusion matrices for the best performing proposed model (Xception + Probe information) and the best performing base CNN model (EfficientNetB4).	30
4.4	F1-score (%) achieved for the proposed and the baseline models in relation to the number of parameters of each model.	32
5.1	Sample X-ray images.	37
5.2	Proposed neural network architecture for the (a) Baseline approach, (b) Approach 1, (c) Approach 2.	40
5.3	Precision vs. Recall for the Baseline approach and Approaches 1 and 2 for end-to-end training.	46
5.4	Aggregated confusion matrices for Approach 1 (end-to-end training).	47
5.5	Grad-CAM visualisation for the COVID-19 class using the EfficientNetB4-based Approach 1 model for four chest X-ray images.	47
6.1	Sample X-ray images from the examined data sets: (a, b) Kermany, (c) Tuberculosis, (d, e) COVID-19 radiography, (f) COVIDx.	51
6.2	Overview of the proposed IEViT model.	52
6.3	Confusion matrices for all the IEViT variants for the four examined datasets. Results refer to the test set of each dataset.	57
6.4	F1-score (%) achieved for each data set and model variant vs. the number of parameters (millions) of the model. (a) "Base" variant, (b) "Large" variant.	60
7.1	An overview of the proposed method. CE: Cross-entropy, IoU: Intersection over the Union, FC: Fully-connected.	64
7.2	Pathology localisation results for the examined IoU thresholds.	67
7.3	Visualisation of pathology localisation for a randomly selected CXR image for each pathology. Green and red denote the ground-truth and the predicted bounding box, respectively, using the proposed CLN-CheXNet model.	69
7.4	Pathology localisation and classification results for the four examined variants of the proposed model in relation to the λ hyperparameter. Values in the y axis depict mean IoU accuracy for the $T(IoU)$ series, and AUC score for the AUC series.	70

List of Tables

4.1	Classification performance (%) of the baseline and the proposed methods for various base CNN models. Results in bold indicate the best performance for each metric and approach. Underlined results indicate the overall best performance.	30
4.2	Difference (Δ) between the metrics' values achieved for the proposed method and the base CNN method.	32
5.1	Classification performance (%) of the examined deep neural network architectures following the baseline approach.	42
5.2	Classification performance (%) of the examined deep neural network architectures following Approach 1 when using the pre-trained weights for the base network and when training each network end-to-end.	42
5.3	Classification performance (%) of the examined deep neural network architectures following Approach 2 when using the pre-trained weights for the base network and when training each network end-to-end.	43
5.4	Confusion matrix for the EfficientNetB4-based Approach 1 (end-to-end) without additional training or fine-tuning on the unseen COVID-19 data set	44
5.5	Execution time and size of best performing models.	44
5.6	Classification performance (%) of the best configurations versus other works using the same data set for the same task.	44
6.1	Data set details	51
6.2	Details of the ViT and IEViT model variants	53
6.3	Data augmentation procedure.	54
6.4	Classification performance (%) on the Kermany et al. children pneumonia data set.	55
6.5	Classification performance (%) on the Tuberculosis data set.	56
6.6	Classification performance (%) on the COVID-19 radiography data set.	56
6.7	Classification performance (%) on the COVIDx data set.	56
6.8	F1-scores (%) and their difference (Δ) for IEViT and ViT for all examined data sets.	57
6.9	F1-scores (%) for each data set using IEViT variants and the examined CNN models.	58
6.10	Best performing IEViT model per data set.	59
7.1	Pathology localisation results using state-of-the-art methods and the proposed method for four different backbone models on the NIH chest X-ray dataset. Results are measured by IoU accuracy at a fixed threshold ([0.1,0.7]).	68
7.2	AUC scores for the annotated subset of the NIH dataset for the task of CXR image classification. Results ordered by ascending mean AUC. Methods in bold are also included in the localisation performance comparison.	69

List of Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AUC	Area Under the Curve
CAD	Computer-Aided Diagnosis
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
CT	Computed Tomography
CV	Computer Vision
CXR	Chest Xray
DNN	Deep Neural Network
DL	Deep Learning
FC	Fully Connected
FN	False Negative
FP	False Positive
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
LUS	Lung Ultra Sound
ML	Machine Learning
MRI	Magnetic Resonance Imaging
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
SVM	Support Vector Machine
TN	True Negative
TP	True Positive
ViT	Vision Transformer

List of Publications

On the use of deep learning for imaging-based COVID-19 detection using chest X-rays. Okolo, G. I., Katsigiannis, S., Althobaiti, T. Ramzan, N., 24 Aug 2021, In: Sensors. 21, 17, 20 p., 5702.

IEViT: an input enhanced vision transformer architecture for chest X-ray image classification. Okolo, G. I., Katsigiannis, S. Ramzan, N., 30 Nov 2022, In: Computer Methods and Programs in Biomedicine. 226, 11 p., 107141.

Multi-modal lung ultrasound image classification by fusing image-based features and probe information. Okolo, G. I., Katsigiannis, S. Ramzan, N., 14 Dec 2022, Proceedings - IEEE 22nd International Conference on Bioinformatics and Bioengineering, BIBE 2022. IEEE, p. 45-50 6 p. (IEEE Proceedings).

CLN: A multi-task deep neural network for chest X-ray image localisation and classification. Okolo, G. I., Katsigiannis, S. Ramzan, N., Submitted for Publication.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Medical imaging methods have been employed for the early detection, diagnosis, and treatment of diseases over several decades. These methods include computed tomography (CT), magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), ultrasound, and X-ray [41]. Medical imaging advancement, has significantly increased our knowledge of human anatomy, physiology, and disease patterns. In the clinic, radiologists and other medical professionals interpret medical images majority of the time [102]. Researchers and medical professionals have started to gain from computer-assisted diagnosis due to the huge variances in pathology and the probable exhaustion of human expertise. Finding or learning relevant features that accurately characterise the regularities or patterns in medical images play a crucial role in a variety of tasks in medical image analysis. Traditionally, the majority of relevant or task-related features were created by human specialists using their understanding of the target domains.

Machine learning has, however, overcome this difficulty by fusing the feature engineering stage with the learning step. That is, deep learning identifies features using only a set of data and some little preprocessing, as needed, as opposed to manually extracting features [146]. Because computers are now responsible for feature engineering, non-experts in machine learning can use deep learning applications, particularly in the field of medical image analysis.

Machine learning algorithms have the potential to enhance diagnostic accuracy in medical image analysis. They can aid in the detection, segmentation, and classification of abnormalities in medical images, leading to more precise and early diagnoses [24]. Automating the analysis of medical images through machine learning can significantly reduce the time and cost associated with manual interpretation. This can help streamline the workflow of healthcare professionals and improve patient care.

Machine learning techniques can assist in developing personalized treatment plans based on individual patient characteristics. By analyzing medical images, algorithms can predict patient outcomes and help tailor treatment strategies accordingly. With the increasing availability of medical imaging data, machine learning can efficiently analyze large datasets and uncover patterns, trends, and associations that may not be readily apparent to human observers. This can contribute to medical research and population health studies.

The exceptional success of machine learning is mostly attributable to the following improvements in learning algorithms, massive data, and graphics processing units (GPUs) [250], [117]. Theoretically speaking, deep learning is superior than traditional artificial neural networks [9] because it makes it possible to build networks with several (more than two) layers. Higher-level features can be obtained from lower-level features thanks to the hierarchical feature representations that deep neural networks can find [146]. Deep learning has achieved record-breaking performance in a range of artificial intelligence applications [66], [258], [303] and grand challenges [221] because these techniques allow hierarchical feature representations to be learnt entirely from data.

Deep learning is specifically used in medical image analysis for lesion/landmark detection [198], [268], [74], image fusion [252], image registration [292], image annotation [241], image segmentation [303], microscopic image analysis [74], image classification and detection [282]. This is because advances in computer vision have made it possible to analyse medical images more accurately [89].

1.2 Research Questions

- What are the recent advancements in the application of AI and Machine/Deep Learning in medical imaging?
- What are the major challenges and limitations faced in the application of AI and Machine Learning in medical imaging?
- How to improve the generalization abilities of deep neural networks on medical image datasets?
- How can neural networks be optimized to detect patterns and features associated with diseases in medical image datasets?

1.3 Research Objectives

The objectives of this thesis can be summarised as follows:

- Compile a thorough literature review of Artificial Intelligence and Machine/Deep Learning applications in medical imaging. This will also highlight state-of-the-art implementations and results in medical image analysis.
- Improve deep neural network generalization abilities on medical image data sets by artificially generating samples via affine transformation techniques, initializing model parameters with pre-trained models from non-medical or natural images as features extractors (transfer learning), and then fine-tuning the network parameters with the task-related samples.
- Develop neural networks to detect patterns and features associated with diseases and health conditions on medical image datasets. Thereby automating the process of Medical Image Analysis to support clinicians in their task of making appropriate decisions.
- Develop state of the art deep learning networks that can effectively perform the tasks of classification, detection and localization of several diseases and pathologies from medical image datasets.
- Evaluation of the performance and validity of the developed Machine/deep learning neural networks and comparison with the state of art.

1.4 Summary of Contributions

- A CNN based model [186] is developed for a multi-modal lung ultrasound image classification by fusing image-based features and probe information. In this work, a multi-modal approach for lung ultrasound image classification that combines image-based features with information about the type of ultrasound probe used to acquire the input image was proposed. We experimented on a large lung ultrasound image dataset that contains images acquired with a linear or a convex ultrasound probe demonstrated the superiority of the proposed approach for the task of classifying lung ultrasound images as “COVID-19” “Normal”, “Pneumonia”, or “Other”, when compared to simply using image-based features. Classification accuracy reached 99.98% using the proposed combination of the Xception pre-trained CNN model with the ultrasound probe Information, as opposed to 96.81% when only the pre-trained EfficientNetB4 CNN model was used. Furthermore, the experimental results demonstrated a consistent improvement in classification performance when combining the examined base CNN models with probe Information, indicating the efficiency of the proposed approach.
- A CNN based system [187] is developed for imaging-based Covid-19 detection using chest X-rays. In this work, eleven deep convolutional neural network architectures were examined for the task of classifying chest X-ray images as belonging to healthy

individuals, individuals with COVID-19 or individuals with viral pneumonia. All the examined networks are established architectures that have been proven to be efficient in image classification tasks, we evaluated three different adjustments to modify the architectures for the task at hand by expanding them with additional layers. The proposed approaches were evaluated for all the examined architectures on a dataset with real chest X-ray images, reaching the highest classification accuracy of 98.04% and the highest F1-score of 98.22% for the best-performing setting.

- A deep learning architecture [185] is developed “IEViT: An Input Enhanced Vision Transformer Architecture for Chest X-ray Image Classification”. In this work the performance of the Vision Transformer (ViT) state-of-the-art image classification machine learning model were examined for the task of chest X-ray image classification, and then we proposed and evaluated the Input Enhanced Vision Transformer (IEViT), a novel enhanced ViT model that can achieve improved performance on chest X-ray images associated with various pathologies. we experimented on four chest X-ray image data sets containing various pathologies (tuberculosis, pneumonia, COVID-19) demonstrated that the proposed IEViT model outperformed ViT for all the data sets and variants examined, achieving an F1-score between 96.39% and 100%, and an improvement over ViT of up to +5.82% in terms of F1-score across the four examined data sets IEViT’s maximum sensitivity (recall) ranged between 93.50% and 100% across the four data sets, with an improvement over ViT of up to +3%, whereas IEViT’s maximum precision ranged between 97.96% and 100%.
- A multi-task deep neural network for chest X-ray (CXR) image localisation and classification is developed in this work, we propose the CXR Localisation Network (CLN), a multi-output deep neural network designed for CXR image localisation and classification. Our proposed architecture was trained and evaluated on a subset of the ChestX-ray14 CXR data set, which included bounding box annotations of eight different pathologies from expert radiologists. The results demonstrated that our approach outperformed state-of-the-art methods in both CXR image localisation and classification, achieving a maximum classification mean Area Under the Curve (AUC) score of 0.893 and a maximum localisation mean Intersection over Union (IoU) accuracy of 0.855.

1.5 Thesis Organisation

This thesis is organised as follows:

- Chapter 2 gives a background into artificial intelligence machine/deep learning.
- Chapter 3 is a detailed literature review of machine applications in medical imaging. It also reviews the challenges currently faced and proposed solutions in this domain.
- Chapter 4 discusses the implementation process of the CNN algorithm architecture for a multi-modal lung ultrasound image classification by fusing image-based features and probe information.
- Chapter 5 explains the experiment process carried out in the development of the deep learning model for imaging-based Covid-19 detection using chest X-rays.
- Chapter 6 is detailed explanation of the experiment process in the development of the deep CNN architecture for An Input Enhanced Vision Transformer Architecture for Chest X-ray Image Classification.
- Chapter 7 discusses a multi-task deep neural network technique used for chest X-ray image localisation and classification.
- Chapter 8 conclusions are summarized along with several open issues related to the work presented in this thesis. As part of future work, we give insights about the potential optimization that may further improve the classification and localization performance in all aspects considered throughout this research project.

Chapter 2

Background

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a method that enables computers to replicate or outperform human decision-making and behaviour [124]. As a result, it refers to a variety of tools and methods (such as rule-based systems, case-based reasoning, genetic algorithms, fuzzy models, and multi-agent systems) and is concerned with a variety of central problems, such as knowledge representation, perception, reasoning, learning, planning and communication [122]. The main focus of early AI research was on propositions that were hard-coded in formal languages and that a computer could automatically reason about using rules for logical inference. The knowledge base method is another name for this [88].

2.1 Machine learning

Machine learning (ML) often refers to the idea that a computer programme performs better over time [127]. In order to execute cognitive tasks like object detection or natural language translation, it seeks to automate the process of constructing analytical models. This is accomplished by utilising algorithms that repeatedly learn from training data that is particular to a problem, enabling computers to discover complicated patterns and hidden insights without being explicitly programmed [33]. ML exhibits strong application, particularly in tasks involving high-dimensional data, such as classification, regression, and grouping. It can assist in the production of trustworthy and repeatable conclusions by learning from past calculations and extracting regularities from enormous databases.

2.1.1 Types of Machine learning

Supervised learning

Supervised learning represents a challenge in which a model is used to learn a representation between input samples and a target variable [209]. Systems with supervised learning challenges provide instances of input vectors and the target vectors that they correspond to in the training data. In supervised learning, there are primarily two sorts of issues: classification issues involving regression detection and class mark issues involving significant value detection [120]. Classification is viewed as a supervised learning issue that necessitates class label prediction. Regression is a supervised learning issue that involves foretelling a numerical label [263].

In classification and regression issues, there may be one or more input variables, and input process parameters may be expressed as any type of data, including categorical and numerical data [263]. The MNIST dataset, which consists of handwritten digit pictures as inputs (pixel data), serves as an illustration of a classification issue [171]. Since they are created for supervised machine learning issues, certain machine learning algorithms are referred to as supervised machine learning algorithms. Examples of it include decision trees and support vector machines [13, 171].

The reason why algorithms are referred to be supervised is because, when given input data, they learn by generating predictions, and those models are managed and enhanced by a method that can help forecast the outcome [193]. Certain approaches, like logistic regression, are best suited for classification, while others, like artificial neural networks, may be used for both classification and regression with just modest adjustments [121, 189].

Unsupervised learning

Unsupervised learning highlights a few issues with using a data relationship model that adds or eliminates data associations. In contrast to supervised learning, which uses outputs and goal variables, unsupervised learning just uses the input data [236]. There are many different approaches to unsupervised learning, but they all have two common problems that practitioners commonly run into: clustering, which involves grouping the data, and estimating range, which requires summarising the distribution of the data. In order to discover data for classes, clustering is shown as an unsupervised learning task [62, 121, 202, 236]. A clustering method commonly in use is called K-Means, where k stands for the cluster centres that may be located in the data [173]. Kernel Density Estimation, a type of density neural network, estimates the distribution of novel points in the issue space using small groups of closely related data samples [121, 141]. Clustering and density estimation may both be used to discover trends in information. Other unsupervised techniques can also be applied, such as visualisation, which involves different kinds of methods for charting or displaying findings, and projection techniques, which include reducing the dimensionality of that data [7].

Reinforcement learning

Reinforcement Learning (RL) is a type of machine learning where an agent learns to make decisions by performing actions in an environment to achieve a goal. The agent receives feedback in the form of rewards or penalties, which guide its learning process. [11]. The algorithms used in reinforcement learning include deep reinforcement learning, Q-learning, and temporal-difference learning [12].

2.1.2 Model Selection

The complexity and amount of parameters that can be changed vary amongst machine learning models. Due to the overfitting issue, the training set is not a reliable indicator to assess the prediction performance of various parameter values. Alternatively, the dataset can be split into three sections if there is enough information. The initial portion of the data, referred to as the training set, is used to train the model with various hyper-parameter values. As the second portion of the data is not utilised for training, it may be used to compare the various hyper-parameter settings and choose the one that has the highest rated prediction performance. A third portion of the data, referred to as the test set, is required to fully assess the chosen model in terms of generalization. Cross-validation is a different method that splits the dataset into two parts: the training set and the test set. This method is particularly useful when the amount of data is constrained and training should make use of as much of the available data as feasible. Cross-validation comes in a variety of forms, but they all have the same fundamental concept. K-fold cross-validation, which randomly divides the training set into k groups, is a popular kind. A set of models are trained on $k-1$ groups and then assessed on the remaining group. Each group goes through this procedure once again, resulting in a final evaluation of every group. The model is chosen based on the aggregate performance scores obtained from all runs. The performance of the chosen model is then assessed using the test set. In addition to the k-fold cross-validation method, another particular form is the leave-one-out method, where k is set to be the same as the number of samples [33].

Computational factors may also be taken into account in addition to the validation error, which serves as a stand-in for the generalization error. Limited computing resources, for example, might affect the choice of value intervals to take into account. Several methods, including coordinate descent, multi-resolution search, grid search, and random search, can be used to optimise hyper-parameters. One hyper-parameter at a time, always starting with the best hyper-parameter configuration currently available, is altered in the coordinate descent technique. To put it simply, the grid search is a thorough search of all possible combinations of the chosen hyper-parameters, the random search is an alternative, where each hyper-parameter is individually sampled from a previous distribution (for example, uniform distribution, inside the interval of interest) and all parameters are altered at once (in

contrast to grid search), a grid search may not be as effective as random sampling, especially if there are more than two or three hyper-parameters. The qualitative examination of the findings, however, is more challenging [9]. The goal of a multi-resolution search is to begin with huge steps of the hyper-parameters. One can start with one of the "best configurations" once many of them have been identified, then look more closely at the areas around to fine-tune the arrangement (by taking smaller steps) [28].

2.1.3 Preprocessing data

Preprocessing is a typical stage in machine learning, as noted in Coates [63]. Depending on the nature of input data, several techniques can be utilised, such as Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Whitening. This section outlines the fundamental concepts of preprocessing and explains how and why preprocessing may enhance the effectiveness of machine learning techniques.

Normalization of Data

Calculating an example's mean value (across all dimensions) and deducting it from each dimension constitute a straight forward preprocessing step in machine learning [63]. This may be thought of as normalising of brightness for images. The total brightness information of a picture is not necessary for all purposes, therefore this normalisation is suitable (e.g. object-recognition tasks [200]). The standard deviation of an example is calculated, and then the example is divided by this result [63]. This has the ability to normalise contrast in images (as mentioned in Coates et al. [64]).

Principal Component Analysis

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is used for reducing dimensionality, while retaining as much information as possible [126]. While the amount of input features may affect the runtime of machine learning algorithms, this can be helpful in reducing runtime. Finding a more compact representation of the data is the basic goal of PCA [140].

Whitening

Whitening discovers interesting regularities in the images, which is one justification for doing whitening on the data [140]. A machine learning model will learn these correlations rather than find other valuable qualities when photos are used as input data and close pixels show a significant link. This is true as long as these correlations are left in place after preprocessing.

2.1.4 K-Nearest Neighbor Approach

One categorization method that is extremely logical, easy to comprehend, and effective in practise is the K-nearest neighbour technique [67]. According to the labels of the k nearest neighbours, a new (unlabeled) data point is categorised in the classification problem [67], [176]. It is now possible to separate the classification of a new point into two steps: The k closest neighbours must be identified first. The effectiveness of this procedure depends on the chosen distance metric to find the closest neighbours (e.g., Manhattan distance, Euclidean distance). There are several methods to calculate the distance between two samples. Following the identification of the labels of the k nearest neighbours in the preceding phase, the class of the new data point must be established [67], [176]. In addition to the simple majority vote, there are several approaches to choose the final class from the k nearest neighbours [67].

2.1.5 Support Vector Machines Approach

Support Vector Machines (SVMs) were initially presented by Boser et al. in 1992 [39] and quickly gained popularity for resolving classification and regression tasks [31]. In its simplest form, for classification, SVMs find a hyperplane that best separates different classes

of data points with the widest possible margin. The data points closest to the hyperplane, which are critical in defining the placement of it, are known as support vectors [176].

2.1.6 Decision Trees and Extremely Randomized Trees

Due to their simplicity and ability to be applied to classification or regression issues, tree-based models are often utilised [176]. The traditional decision tree is a model that calculates a goal value using a set of binary choice rules. An attribute of the input sample is evaluated at each node of the decision tree. When categorising fresh data samples, the decision tree checks each attribute at each node at each step and selects the branch that will come next based on the actual value of the property [176]. This is carried out up until a leaf node, where each leaf node represents a distinct class.

2.2 Deep learning

Deep Learning is a subset of machine learning where artificial neural networks, algorithms inspired by the human brain, learn from large amounts of data. Deep learning models automatically extract and learn features from raw data, improving their tasks without human intervention. These models are called "deep" because they use many layers of neural networks to process data, enabling them to capture complex patterns and make sophisticated decisions [273]. Deep learning's development roots may be found in the work of Walter Pitts and Warren McCulloch (1943), the backpropagation model (1961), the convolutional neural network model (1978), the LSTM (long short-term memory) (1996), AlexNet (2010) [142]. Deep learning techniques are now seeing an exponential growth because of massively layered neural networks and the use of GPUs to speed up their execution.

2.2.1 Deep Neural Network

A Deep Neural Network (DNN) is a type of artificial neural network with multiple layers between the input and output layers. These intermediate, or "hidden," layers enable the DNN to learn complex patterns in large amounts of data. [265].

Basic Concept

A single neuron, in the context of neural networks in artificial intelligence, is a basic processing unit that mimics the function of a biological neuron. It receives one or more inputs, processes them, and produces an output. Each input is assigned a weight, which is adjusted during the learning process. The neuron applies a function (often nonlinear) to the weighted sum of its inputs to generate the output. This function is called an activation function, and it determines whether the neuron should be activated or not, based on the input it receives. [139]. In Figure 2.1 the fundamental of a single neuron is depicted. Using the illustration in Figure 2.1 as an example, the neuron receives various inputs x_i and computes the following output:

$$output = \left(\sum_{i=1}^3 w_i x_i + b \right) \quad (2.1)$$

In the depicted neural network diagram, we have a single neuron with three distinct inputs denoted by x_1 , x_2 , and x_3 . Each input is associated with a corresponding weight; these are w_1 , w_2 , and w_3 respectively. Additionally, there is a bias term b , which is crucial for adjusting the output independently of the inputs. The neuron calculates the weighted sum of its inputs, which is the sum of each input multiplied by its weight plus the bias. This sum then passes through a non-linear function, often referred to as an activation function, to introduce non-linearity into the neuron's output. This activation function allows the neuron to make complex decisions by enabling it to capture and model non-linear relationships within the data. The final output of the neuron, represented as y , is the result of the activation function applied to the weighted sum. This output can then be used as an input to subsequent layers in a deeper network, or as a final output in a single-layer network.

FIGURE 2.1: Illustration of a single neuron with four input values x_1, x_2, x_3, b .

Multilayer Perceptron

A Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) is a type of artificial neural network used in machine learning. It consists of at least three layers of nodes: an input layer, one or more hidden layers, and an output layer. Each node, except for the input nodes, is a neuron that uses a nonlinear activation function. MLP utilizes a supervised learning technique called backpropagation for training. Its multiple layers and non-linear activation distinguish MLP from a linear perceptron. [139]. The straightforward example for a of MLP in Figure 2.2 The rightmost layer is known as the output layer, whereas the leftmost layer is known as the input layer and the middle layer is referred to as a hidden layer [176], [139].

FIGURE 2.2: Example of a multilayer perceptron.

Gradient Descent and Error Backpropagation

Gradient Descent is an optimization technique that minimizes a function by iteratively moving towards the steepest descent, guided by the negative gradient. In machine learning, it adjusts the model's parameters to minimize the cost function, starting with random values and progressively refining them by computing the gradient of the cost and updating the parameters in the direction that reduces the cost. Error Backpropagation, often paired with Gradient Descent in neural networks, involves a forward pass where inputs are processed to produce an output, followed by a backward pass where the error (the difference between the predicted and actual outputs) is propagated back through the network. This backward pass efficiently computes the gradients of the cost function with respect to all weights, which are then used to update the parameters, thereby training the neural network to minimize prediction errors [176].

Avoid Overfitting- Regularization

The data set and intended prediction job typically dictate the number of input and output units, however the amount of hidden units and the number of hidden layers can be varied [176]. The number of hidden units determines how many variables are modifiable, and hence, how large the model may be. Selecting the ideal number of hidden units, which prevents both underfitting and overfitting, would be the first step in controlling the model's complexity [28]. This modification of the training criterion tries to reduce generalisation error while controlling the complexity of neural networks. Another strategy for managing model complexity and preventing overfitting is early stopping. This technique's concept is to utilise a validation set to evaluate the model's performance as it is being trained [30]. The value of the error function is iteratively decreased throughout the training process taking into account the gradient descent approach. The measured error on the validation set will decrease up to a certain point, but after that point, overfitting on the training data will cause the measured error to grow. The goal is now to end training before convergence (for example, when the validation error achieves its minimum value) by using the measured performance [28].

2.2.2 Convolutional neural network

Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) are supervised learning models that use convolutions to learn higher-order features from the data. A CNN's capacity to create an internal representation of a two-dimensional signal is an advantage. This enables the model to pick up on location and size in different data formats, which is crucial when handling images. CNNs were created to map image information to an output variable, as seen in Figure 2.3. The convolution layer and the sub-sampling layer are the first two layers shown in a CNN. In order to get feature maps, the convolution layer computes the convolution between inputs. After convolution, a nonlinear activation function is applied, followed by a subsampling layer and averaging to minimise the dimension of the feature maps. A collection of CNN layers for classification, recognition, or decision-making follow the subsampling [22]. Convolutional layers, pooling layers, nonlinear activation layers, and fully connected layers make up CNN's fundamental structural components. Typically, the image is preprocessed before being fed into the network through the input layer. After being processed by a number of alternately stacked convolutional layers and pooling layers, the fully connected layer then classifies the image [32].

FIGURE 2.3: Convolutional neural network.

Convolutional layers

The fundamental component of a CNN is the convolutional layer. Its job is to automatically extract valuable features from input images. It typically identifies edges, colours, and low level features in the first layer. The convolutional layers picks up increasingly complicated features as it goes further into the network. Convolutional layer employs a collection of matrices referred to as kernels (sometimes referred to as filters) to represent these characteristics. By design, each of these kernels has the same depth size (i.e., the number of colour channels), but a lower height and width size than the input image.

Each kernel slides across the activations created by the prior layer with a specified step size called a stride during the training phase when we propagate the data forward. The receptive field, which is a constrained area in the input that is the same size as the kernel, is calculated as the dot product between the kernel and the receptive field. An activation map (or feature map) is the name of the output matrix from this technique. A sample of how a 2×2 kernel with a stride of 1 slides over a 3×3 input is shown in Figure 2.4.

FIGURE 2.4: Convolutional Operation.

Pooling layers

In most cases, the pooling layer comes after the convolutional layer. The main purpose is to perform dimensionality reduction (compress activation maps) and downsampling on the input image to lessen the number of connections between convolutional layers, which will ease the load on the network's compute resources [91]. Become aware of the input image's scale, translation, and rotation invariances [267]; Make the output feature map more resistant to a single neuron's distortion and mistake [157]. Max pooling and average pooling are the two pooling techniques that are most frequently employed in practise. According to Figure 2.5, max pooling operates similarly to a convolution by sliding a window over the input data (i.e., activation map), and at each step, we choose the greatest value in the pooling window. On the other hand, average pooling determines the average value in the pooling window at each step. It should be noted that pooling layers lack learnable parameters, which implies that crucial information may be lost during this process. A sample of max pooling with 2×2 pooling window and stride 2 is shown in Figure 2.5.

FIGURE 2.5: Max Pooling Operation 2.

Fully Connected Layer

The Fully Connected (FC) Layer typically comes after the convolutional layer and the pooling layer, and the neurons in its many levels are completely interconnected. It then produces the category information for the image after integrating and categorising the local information using category discrimination that was retrieved after convolution and pooling [228]. It has a number of hidden layers that more intricately extract high-level information from the prior network [300]. The number of categories equals the number of neurons at the output end, and the output vector is then utilised to identify the category to which the image belongs. FC Layer functions in CNNs as a classifier.

Nonlinear Activation Function

The purpose of the activation function is to establish a functional link between the input and output, introducing a nonlinear system into the neural network. A proper nonlinear activation function may considerably enhance the network's performance [91]. The most commonly used activation functions for classification problems are sigmoid and softmax.

Loss Function

The final classification is accomplished using the output layer, which is typically the final layer of the FC layer, in addition to the different layer-types of CNN architecture mentioned in the preceding section. The efficiency of the CNN architecture is further impacted by several loss functions, which are used for various computer vision visual tasks such as image classification and object recognition). Overall, Softmax+Cross-Entropy has established itself as the CNN model's standard loss function [158].

2.3 Image classification

One of the core problems in computer vision and many visual recognition disciplines in recent years is image classification. As classification network performance increases, so does the quality of its applications [257], such as object identification [86], segmentation [163], classification of videos [130]. Promoting the advancement of computer vision includes improving image classification technologies. Its primary processes include classifier design [301], feature extraction and representation [271], and image data preparation [32].

Image feature extraction, the foundation of image classification, has long been the subject of research. Conventional methods for extracting image characteristics place greater emphasis on manually defining individual image attributes. Both the generalizability and portability of this approach are lacking. Hence, researchers envision giving computers the ability to interpret images similarly to human vision. Subsequent studies attempted to learn features using the multilayer perceptron and trained the model using the backpropagation (BP) method [284]. The idea of building a computer neural network resembling a biological visual system was sparked by this discovery, and CNN was subsequently created. The CNN model's first batch, LeNet-5, was introduced by Lecun et al. [147]. Unfortunately, the LeNet-5's identification results on complicated images were not perfect due to a lack of enough training data, as well as limitations imposed by the theoretical underpinnings and computational power [309].

A new chapter in deep learning was opened by Hinton et al [hinton2006fastproposal] of an efficient learning method for multi-hidden-layer neural networks' learning challenges. Later, researchers discovered the convolution operation on the GPU, considerably enhancing the network's computational effectiveness. It grew by two to twenty times more than the CPU's operating speed [61]. Deep learning has since attracted a growing amount of interest. The AlexNet model was created by Krizhevsky et al. based on the LeNet-5 [141]. It outperformed the second-best entry in the ILSVRC2012 ImageNet competition by a significant margin. Researchers started studying CNN more thoroughly after AlexNet excelled in the ImageNet image classification competition. Zeiler and Fergus presented ZFNet as a

visualisation method to comprehend CNNs [300]. Then, during the ILSVRC2014–2017 classification challenge, references [235], [255], [244], [294], [109] produced strong results; they all made outstanding innovations from the outset.

2.4 Optimization Techniques

New methods of optimisation have also been thoroughly researched by researchers in the community following CNN's reintroduction. This section will concentrate on cutting-edge and practical methods for CNN model optimisation that take advantage of their performance and fast training.

2.4.1 Regularization technique

Another frequently used method known as regularisation tries to increase the generality of deep learning models by delivering better test set outcomes [143].

Regularization through data

A popular and efficient method for enhancing the performance of deep learning models on tests is data-based regularisation. The two most common techniques for database regularisation are batch normalisation and dropout. As stated in [117], the modification of parameters in earlier levels causes a change in the distribution of inputs for each layer in deep CNNs. The internal covariate shift is the name given to this phenomena. The models must thus be trained using slower learning rates, which slow down the training, and conservative parameter initialization. Moreover, models with saturating non-linearities brought on by the shift in distribution make it much harder to train these models. In order to effectively transfer the output of each layer into the appropriate domain, batch normalisation was suggested. Regularization also resolves the overfitting issue, which arises frequently when deep CNN models are trained. After the selected model is finished, it is rather typical for there to be much more training parameters than observed data. The trained model's performance will thereafter be excellent on the training set while being appalling on the testing set. Dropout was presented in [250] as a straightforward data-based regularisation technique to avoid overfitting. A fully linked layer's activations are randomly made to be zero during training, forcing the models to pick out more representative features and reducing overfitting. In Figure 2.6 a), a dropout case study, is provided. As the completely linked layers are referred to as hidden layers, which are often employed in ANN. A predetermined parameter called the dropout probability is used to regulate the ratio of active to inactive neurons during the current training session. More neurons are compelled to output zero as activations the higher the likelihood. The probability is typically set at 0.5. The next-layer neurons that are being dropped out are still linked to the neurons that are being dropped out, but their activations are set to zero. For the sake of simplicity, the connections between dropped-out neurons and the neurons in the following layer are disregarded. Similar to DropOut, DropConnect is another drop connection method [272]. Nevertheless, DropConnect zeroes out a randomly chosen portion of the network's weights. As can be seen in Figure 2.6 b), the overfitting issue is then resolved since the neurons in the following layer get a random subset of input from neurons in the preceding layer. There are a number of Dropout variations that have produced empirical evidence [21, 40, 83, 166].

Regularization through network architectures

Deep learning models' innovative designs can also be used as regularisation techniques. Deep learning models become less complex by weight sharing, which enables the reuse of a certain trainable parameter in several regions of the models. The quantity of trainable parameters has been decreased as a result, increasing the generality of deep learning models. Deep learning model performance may also be enhanced by selecting the appropriate activation functions. Dropout is employed as the most common technique for regularization. Another unique sort of regularisation is multitasking [220]. It may be used with semisupervised learning to employ unlabeled data for a different goal [214]. Two approaches that leverage

FIGURE 2.6: Dropout and DropConnect with dropout probability at 0.5.

knowledge sharing to perform regularisation are transfer learning and meta-learning [143, 192]. An additional regularisation technique is the model selection, which seeks to choose the best-trained models based on the assessment outcomes on the validation set. It should be emphasised, nevertheless, that the model that performs the best in this case combines all of the strategies, not simply architecture. Nevertheless, there are additional model selection techniques that use network growth and network pruning to deliberately choose the amount of units in a certain network design [34].

2.5 Transfer Learning

Transfer learning (TL) is a type of learning where a model picks up knowledge from one problem and applies it to another [283]. This is a useful approach for issues when a process near to the primary issue existed and the related task required a lot of data [283]. Due to the importance of huge data sets to deep learning's effectiveness, deep learning models may perform noticeably worse if they have inadequate training data. Transfer learning is consequently used to quickly and cheaply tackle this issue. Transfer learning differs from multi-task training in that the tasks are learnt in order, whereas multi-task training aims to get desired performance from a single model on all tasks simultaneously in comparison. Figure 2.7 illustrates the transfer learning process.

FIGURE 2.7: Transfer Learning Process.

2.5.1 Transfer learning with convolutional neural networks

The concept of transfer learning with CNN proposes that knowledge may be transmitted at the parametric level. Convolutional layer parameters are used by well-trained CNN models to perform a new task in the field of medicine. In TL with CNN for medical image classification, in particular, a medical image classification (target task) may be learnt by utilising

the generic features acquired from the natural image classification (source task), if labels are accessible in both domains. TL involve image analysis with CNN models for supervised medical imaging classification using ImageNet data. There are essentially two Main methods for utilising CNN models: feature extractor or fine-tuning. Although the fine-tuning strategy changes parameters during model fitting, the feature extractor approach freezes the convolutional layers. Four TL techniques are identified since each of them may be further subdivided into two subcategories. In Figure. 2.8, they are intuitively represented.

FIGURE 2.8: Four Transfer Learning Approaches.

2.6 Data Augmentation

Methods including batch normalisation [117], transfer learning [283], and dropout [250] have been developed in an effort to reduce overfitting and enhance the generalisation of trained models. Data augmentation [260], which directly addresses training-set size and has been frequently used, is another beneficial technique to lessen overfitting. Techniques to enlarge and generalise training datasets are referred to as data augmentation [242] as illustrated in Figure 2.9. Geometrical transformations and colour transformations are two examples of image-level augmentation techniques covered in this section. As selecting the best augmentation strategy frequently depends on the unique situation. Geometrical augmentation entails adjustments at the image-level, such as flipping, rotating, and cropping. The two geometrical changes that are most frequently utilised in image analysis to expand the volume of training data are flipping and rotation. Structured characteristics are kept with minimum distortion since the majority of images are orientationally invariant.

FIGURE 2.9: Data Augmentation Process.

Chapter 3

Literature Review

3.1 Medical Imaging

Medical imaging is considered to be a processes that offer visual data about the human body. Medical imaging is used to help clinicians and radiologists diagnose and treat patients more quickly and effectively. Different imaging modalities are used in medical imaging, which plays a significant role in the diagnosis and treatment of disorders. Medical images includes X-rays, computed tomography (CT), magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and ultrasound [101]. These techniques are essential for identifying anatomical and functional details about various human organs for both diagnosis and research [206]. Medical imaging is an indispensable tool in contemporary healthcare environments with its applications in tumour segmentation, classification, detection, medical image annotation, and retrieval. Machine learning plays a crucial role in CAD [3, 4, 84, 172, 223].

3.1.1 Medical Imaging Modalities

The two medical imaging modalities thoroughly examined in this research are as follows:

Radiography: X-rays are used in radiography to see the human anatomy [297]. In particular, a generator creates X-ray beams and directs them towards the person's body. Depending on their densities and compositions, different organs and tissues absorb varying amounts of X-ray energy. Fluoroscopy and projection radiography are the two methods used to create radiographic images. The term "X-rays" also applies to projection radiography.

(a) Frontal, (b) Lateral.

FIGURE 3.1: Chest X-ray images.

Ultrasound: Ultrasonography creates 2D or 3D pictures using high frequency sound waves [262]. The ultrasonic probe produces and transmits pulses of ultrasound waves into the patient's body. At the boundary between several tissues, sound waves are reflected. The ultrasound probe then captures the soundwaves that are reflected in order to create images from them. Due to its low cost and lack of radiation, ultrasound is frequently used to image the heart, abdominal organs, and foetus in pregnant women. Additionally, real-time

(a) Convex, (b) Linear.

FIGURE 3.2: Ultrasound images.

ultrasound picture acquisition is possible. However, due to noise, distortions, and shadows, ultrasound images are typically of low quality.

3.2 Medical Imaging Research Issues and Discussions

The most significant medical imaging-related issues are highlighted in this area, along with various other research topics and directions for the future.

3.2.1 Main Challenges for Medical Imaging

1. **Data Limitations:** The availability of public datasets across numerous disciplines is the biggest problem that researchers frequently encounter. There is still difficulty in attaining large datasets for various chest X-ray pathologies.
2. **Annotation of Clinical Data :** The acquisition of labelled and annotated chest images is also a main problem, according to [254]. We may state that there were few labelled datasets available for chest imaging. It is also a difficult process if a team of radiologists is responsible for creating the labelling dataset. The same dataset was labelled by various radiologists, which caused uncertainty and called for complex algorithms. The majority of patients have many chest diseases, hence this ambiguous data is inaccurate for binary classification and segmentation. The majority of academics keep clear of it because it is challenging to train the model on ambiguous data.
3. **Data imbalance** is one of the biggest problems with the chest pathology detection system. From the publicly accessible datasets, it can be shown that one class has more samples than other classes. Managing enormous image sizes is another difficult task for computer scientists.
4. It costs a lot of money computationally to train the model on large-sized original images. Similar to this, even with GPU hardware, training complex deep learning networks takes time. Choosing an optimised set of hyperparameters, such as the number of layers, depth size, kernel size, number of filters, filter size, etc., is another obstacle to employing a deep learning model.

3.2.2 Directions for Medical Imaging

Numerous deep learning (DL) techniques based on convolutional networks (CNN) have been proposed for the classification of lung diseases and chest X-ray screening [245][203][195]. These methods help radiologists identify worrisome areas, analyse common pathologies, and get around bias and perception issues. However, these strategies are specialised to certain diseases, such as tuberculosis [195], pneumonia [121], and lung cancer [16]. As a result, developing a deep learning model to identify various chest diseases from CXR remains difficult and calls for more research. There are various deep learning-based methods that can identify various chest diseases in the literature.

This review gives specifics on the deep learning approaches used to identify both common and rare chest pathologies. Over the past years, a substantial amount of work that uses deep learning approaches to lessen the difficulty of unique characteristics was presented. Earlier CAD techniques can analyse chest radiographs to find one or more diseases. However, the deep learning approach can simultaneously analyse the appearance data of many diseases directly from chest scans, aiding radiologists in their interpretation. Meanwhile, the research covered in this section's discussion of deep learning approaches highlights some significant difficulties.

3.3 Machine Learning in Medical Imaging

Medical imaging is a crucial diagnostic tool. In 1895, Roentgen discovered that X-rays could be used to examine the human body without causing any harm. Shortly after, X-ray radiography became the first diagnostic imaging technique. Since then, a variety of imaging modalities have been created, with computed tomography, ultrasound, magnetic resonance imaging, and positron emission tomography being some of the most widely used. Moreover, increasingly intricate imaging techniques have been created. At numerous points in the patient care process, including detection, classification, staging, treatment response evaluation, monitoring of disease recurrence, as well as directing interventional treatments, surgeries, and radiation therapy, image information is vital to decision-making.

Beginning in the 1960s, attempts were made to use computers to automatically interpret medical images [137, 234, 249, 286]. Research showed that using a computer to analyse medical images was feasible, but the work received little attention, most likely due to the lack of access to high-quality digitised image data and computing resources. Chan et al. [45] created a computer-aided diagnosis (CAD) system for mammography microcalcification identification and carried out the first observer performance research [46] that showed how well CAD improved breast radiologists' performance in finding microcalcifications.

3.4 Applications of Machine Learning for Computer Aided Diagnosis (CAD) in Medical Imaging

The development of CAD systems uses machine learning techniques. Image analysis techniques were used in the traditional machine learning approach to CAD in medical imaging to identify illness patterns and identify various classes of structures, such as normal and abnormal, on the images. Based on domain expertise, CAD developers create image processing and feature extraction algorithms to describe the image features that may differentiate between the various states. The competence of the mathematical formulations or empirical image analysis approaches that are meant to convert the image features to numerical values, as well as the domain experience of the CAD developers, are frequently factors that affect how well the feature descriptors perform. The classifier uses the extracted features as input predictor variables, and a predictive model is created by varying the weights of the different features based on the statistical characteristics of a series of training samples to calculate the likelihood that an image belongs to one of the states. Even if they have seen a lot of cases from the patient population, the human developer might not be able to transform the complicated illness patterns into a finite number of feature descriptors using the conventional machine learning technique. Also, it may be challenging for the manually created characteristics to withstand the wide fluctuations of normal and aberrant patterns. The performance of the designed CAD system is frequently constrained by its capacity to discriminate or generalise, leading to a high rate of false positives at high sensitivity or inversely.

In many applications, deep learning has become the cutting-edge machine learning technique. Deep learning is a kind of representation learning technique in which a sophisticated multilayer neural network architecture automatically learns data representations by abstracting the input data at various layers [146]. Deep convolutional neural networks (DCNN) are the most widely utilised deep learning networks for pattern identification tasks in pictures. By iteratively modifying its weights through backpropagation, DCNN may

be taught to automatically extract pertinent features from the training samples for a specific job. Hence, DCNN does not require explicitly constructed features as input and instead learns feature representations during training. The DCNN features should outperform hand-engineered features in terms of selectivity and invariance if they are correctly trained using a sizable training set that is representative of the sample of interest [146]. Deep learning can easily examine millions of cases that even human specialists would not be able to view and memorise in their lifetimes since the learning process is automated. As long as the training set is big and diverse enough for it to evaluate, deep learning can therefore be more resilient to the vast range of changes in characteristics across distinct classes to be discriminated.

CNN has its roots in the neocognitron that Fukushima et al. proposed in the early 1980s [82]. In 1990 [148], LeCun trained a CNN using backpropagation to identify patterns of handwritten digits. In the early 1990s, CNN was employed in several applications, including object identification, character recognition, and face recognition. In 1993, Lo et al. trained a CNN to recognise lung nodules in chest radiographs, which was the first time CNN had been used to analyse medical pictures [161, 162]. Chan et al. used CNN for mass detection [47, 224, 226] the next year and for microcalcification identification [44, 48] on mammograms in the same year. In 1994, Zhang et al. used a similar shift-invariant neural network to find clusters of microcalcifications [304]. The pattern identification capabilities of CNN in medical images were proven, despite the fact that these early CNNs were not particularly sophisticated.

Deep CNN was made possible by a number of crucial neural network training methods that have been developed over time, including layer-wise unsupervised pre-training followed by supervised fine-tuning [29, 77, 104], the use of rectified linear unit (ReLU) [87, 179] as an activation function in place of sigmoid-type activation functions, pooling to improve feature invariance and reduce dimensionality [213], dropout to reduce overfitting [250], and batch normalisation [117] that These methods enable the training of neural networks with ever more layers and weights. In 2012, Krizhevsky et al. [141] proposed a CNN with five convolutional layers and three fully connected layers (named "AlexNet") that contained more than 60 million weights. This CNN outperformed previous models in the ImageNet Large Scale Visual Recognition Challenge (ILSVRC) [221], which classified more than 1000 classes of common objects on photographic images. AlexNet exhibited the deep structure's several layers' capacity for pattern recognition. Since AlexNet, DCNNs have been built with increasing depth. A residual network (ResNet) with 110–152 layers was demonstrated to beat a number of previous DCNNs by He et al. [100], who also introduced residual learning. ResNet was the winner of the ILSVRC in 2015. According to Sun et al [253], a DCNN's learning ability grew with depth, but it could only be used with large training data.

Several medical image analysis tasks for CAD have used deep learning [154, 170, 225]. The categorization of illness and normal patterns, the classification of malignant and benign lesions, and the prediction of high- and low-risk patterns of developing cancer in the future are the most popular applications of deep learning in CAD. Additional uses included the segmentation and classification of various organs and tumour types, the classification of alterations in tumour size or texture for the evaluation of treatment response, or the prognosis or recurrence prediction. Research for lung illnesses and breast cancer were carried out utilising the public data sets since there exist sizable public data sets for chest radiography, thoracic CT, and mammograms. Moreover, fundus pictures, optical computed tomography, and histopathology images have all been subjected to deep learning-based image processing in order to diagnose eye illnesses [68, 125]. The majority of the experiments presented extremely encouraging findings, adding to the excitement around deep-learning-based CAD. Although this new generation of CAD tools is referred as AI, they are far from being "intelligent," instead behaving like an extremely complicated mathematical model that memorises data in its millions of weights.

3.5 Chest X-ray Images

Chest X-ray (CXR) imaging is one of the most widely utilised medical imaging techniques for detecting and diagnosing diseases [248], including pneumonia, tuberculosis, COVID-19,

malignancy, and others [17, 232, 295]. Its great advantage lies in its relatively low cost, high accessibility, and easy operation [203]. Important information about a patient's health can be extracted from chest X-ray images, and manual analysis and detection by chest X-ray imaging of marks and signs of diseases is done by expert radiologists. Interpretations can be difficult and it is a long and complicated process. In addition, the requirement for expert radiologists can be a bottleneck, especially in remote or deprived areas. To address this issue, recent research has focused on the use of machine learning methods for automated diagnosis, with various approaches gaining popularity and aiming to become an important tool for clinicians [80, 90, 131, 154].

The cutting edge development of general-purpose graphics processing unit (GPU) hardware [246], medical image analysis techniques [239], and deep learning techniques [76], has allowed scientists to automatically detect diseases using chest X-ray images [210], and design powerful computer-aided diagnosis (CAD) systems [25, 159, 282]. The potential gains from automated X-ray diagnosis are increased sensitivity for findings, automation of tedious daily tasks, prioritisation of time-sensitive cases, and solving the issue of radiologists not always being available in remote areas or developing countries [42]. Chest X-ray imaging is also relatively cheap and accessible, with modern digital radiography machines being affordable even in under-developed countries [203].

3.6 Deep Learning for Chest X-ray Images Classification and Detection

The use of deep learning has proven to be very effective and reliable in revealing features, which are not evident, in images. Deep learning is currently widely used in the medical field for image classification and detection of human diseases through computer-aided diagnosis [89, 128, 159, 282]. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) have demonstrated beneficial learning and useful feature extraction capabilities, and thus have been embraced by many researchers [142]. The use of pre-trained networks on labelled medical images to train CNNs on disease classification has been proven to result in high performance, suggesting that in some cases, CNNs have achieved a level that is equivalent to or even better than certified human radiologists [145, 210, 211]. CNNs have been applied on chest X-ray images for the diagnosis of pneumonia [177], for cystoscopic image recognition extraction [181], for automated detection of polyps during colonoscopy [275] etc.

Transfer learning has also proven to be very efficient in deep learning applications, making it possible to use pre-trained networks from different applications in order to save time and power in training a model to achieve high performance. This concept was utilised by Vikash et al. [54] in pneumonia detection utilising pre-prepared models trained on the ImageNet [221] data set. Xianghong et al. [92] modified the VGG16 model and used it for identification of lung regions and classification of various kinds of pneumonia. Ronneburger et al. [217] implemented a CNN with a small set of images but applying a data augmentation technique to attain a better result. They applied the u-net to a cell segmentation task on two data sets, namely "PhC-U373" [73] and "DIC-HeLa" [86], and achieved an average IOU score of 92% and 77.5% respectively. Ho et al. [105] reported an accurate identification of 14 thoracic diseases using feature extraction techniques and the pre-trained DenseNet-121 [112] model. Lakhani et al. [145] also carried out an experiment for pulmonary TB detection using GoogleNet [255] and AlexNet [142] by applying image augmentation techniques and attained an Area Under Curve (AUC) accuracy of 99%.

Wang et al. [280] carried out an experiment using chest X-ray data, labelled with eight diseases, and trained a deep CNN model by utilising weight parameters from VGGNet-16 [244], AlexNet [142], ResNet-50 [100] and GoogLeNet [255]. The ResNet-50 showed better results than other models in the classification of 7 diseases except for 1, for which AlexNet performed better. Some of the AUC scores are as follows: "Cardiomegaly" (81.41%), "Pneumothorax" (78.91%), "Effusion" (73.62%), "Nodule" (71.64%), "Atelectasis" (70.69%).

Narin et al. [180] carried out an experiment on chest X-ray images, using the Inception-ResNetV2 [256], InceptionV3 [257] and ResNet-50 [100] for the classification of COVID-19 and normal images. The ResNet50 model achieved the best classification accuracy of 98%, the InceptionV3 97% and the Inception-ResNetV2 87%. Wang et al. [274] presented a deep

learning CNN architecture, called COVID-Net for COVID-19 detection from chest X-rays, achieving a 92.4% accuracy.

Chowdhury et al. [55] carried out two COVID-19-related experiments with a chest X-ray data set. The first utilised two classes, normal and COVID-19, while the second utilised three classes, namely COVID-19, viral pneumonia and normal. They experimented using transfer learning with and without image augmentation, and tested and validated their approach using 8 pre-trained networks. Classification accuracy reached 99.41% for the 2-class problem without image augmentation and 99.70% with image augmentation, while for the 3-class problem, classification accuracy reached 97.74% without image augmentation and 97.94% with image augmentation.

The use of chest X-rays for COVID-19 detection has been the focus of multiple other recent studies. Shibly et al. [240] proposed the use of VGG16 [244] and Faster R-CNN framework to detect COVID-19 from chest X-rays, achieving an accuracy of 97.36%, sensitivity of 97.65%, and precision of 99.28%. Jain et al. [120] used the ResNet101 model, achieving a 98.93% accuracy, 98.93% sensitivity, 98.66% specificity, 96.39% precision, and 98.15% F1-score. Nishio et al. [184] proposed a chest X-ray-based computer-aided diagnosis (CADx) system for classification into COVID-19 pneumonia, non-COVID-19 pneumonia and normal. They experimented using the VGG16 [244], MobileNet [230], DenseNet-121 [112], and EfficientNet [259] CNN models, and reported that VGG16 performed best with an accuracy of 83.6%. Similarly, Apostolopoulos et al. [13] experimented with the VGG19 [244], MobileNetv2 [230], Inception [257], Xception [52] and InceptionResNetv2 [256] CNNs, reporting that MobileNetv2 performed best with an accuracy of 96.78%, 98.66% sensitivity, and 96.46% specificity. Sahlol et al. [227] attempted to reduce the computational complexity of CNN-based approaches by combining CNN-based features with the Marine Predators Algorithm for swarm-based feature selection. Experiments on two different chest X-ray data sets demonstrated a maximum accuracy of 98.7%.

Apart from X-rays, other approaches have also been employed for COVID-19 detection. For example, considering that cough is a vital symptom of COVID-19, Chuma et al. [57] carried out an experiment on a cough classification task using a K-band continuous-wave Doppler radar sensor and the AlexNet [142], VGG-19 [244], and GoogLeNet [255] CNN architectures, reporting that AlexNet performed best, with an accuracy of 88% when people were 1 m away from the sensor, 80% for 3 m, and 86.5% when data for mixed 1 m and 3 m.

Sharma et al. [238] and Stephen et al. [269] used CNNs for the purpose of detecting pneumonia in chest X-ray images, achieving an accuracy of 90.68% and 93.73% respectively. Khan et al.'s [135] CoroNet CNN-based architecture achieved an overall accuracy of 89.6% for the same task. Saraiva et al. [231] used a multilayer perceptron (MLP) and a CNN for the same task, achieving an average accuracy of 92.16% with the MLP, and 94.40% with the CNN, whereas Ayan et al. [20] used the well-known Xception and VGG16 CNN models, along with transfer learning and fine-tuning techniques for training, with test results showing that VGG16 outperformed Xception, reaching accuracies of 87% and 82% respectively. In a later work, Ayan et al. [19] proposed a CNN-based ensemble method, achieving an accuracy of 95.83%. Liang et al. [152] combined dilated convolutions and residual approaches, achieving an accuracy of 90%. Okolo et al. [187] examined the use of various CNN architectures to detect COVID-19 and viral pneumonia in chest X-rays, achieving a maximum accuracy of 98%.

Tuberculosis diagnosis from chest X-rays using machine learning has also been widely researched. Yadav et al. [296] implemented various deep learning techniques with the aim to detect Tuberculosis in chest X-ray images. Significant improvement was achieved using fine tuning and multiple data augmentation, reaching an accuracy of 94.89%. Deep learning was also used for the same task by Hooda et al. [106], achieving an accuracy of 82.09%, and by Pasa et al. [195], achieving an accuracy of 86.82%, whereas Evalgelista et al.'s [78] proposed CNN-based computer-aided diagnosis approach reached an accuracy of 88.76%. Rahman et al. [208] carried out an experiment for the detection of tuberculosis using various CNN models and transfer learning, achieving an F1-score for the best performing model of 96.47%.

Bar et al. [23] used a DL approach that combined features retrieved by a deep CNN model

with low-level features for diagnosing pleural effusion, cardiomegaly, and normal vs. abnormal cases. Their method achieved an AUC of 93%, 89%, and 79% for pleural effusion, cardiomegaly, and normal vs. abnormal, respectively. Cicero et al. [60] utilised the GoogleNet model, achieving AUC scores between 85%-96.4% for six different pathologies. Wang et al. [280] employed a weak-supervised technique for the classification of eight pathologies on the ChestX-ray8 CXR data set, achieving an average AUC of 80.3%. A DenseNet-121 model (CheXNet) was used in [210] on the ChestX-ray14 data set that contains 14 pathologies, reaching an average AUC of 84.11%. A cascading neural network was utilised by Kumar et al. [144] on the same data set. They used under-sampling and over-sampling strategies to reduce bias resulting from unbalanced data, achieving an average AUC of 79.5%. Majdi et al. [169] proposed a custom DenseNet-121 for identifying cardiomegaly and pulmonary nodules, reaching an AUC of 73% for pulmonary nodule identification, and 92% for cardiomegaly detection. Zhao et al. [305] also worked on the Chest-Xray14 data set and proposed a deep CNN model with attention mechanism (AMDenseNet), achieving an average AUC of 85.37%. Blais and Akhloufi [36] used various models with binary relevance to identify chest pathologies. When combined with the Adam optimiser, the Xception deep CNN model outperformed other models, reaching a mean AUC of 95.87% on 6 pathologies and 94.90% on the CheXpert data set's 14 pathologies. Okolo et al. [185] proposed an enhanced version of the Vision Transformer for CXR image classification and evaluated it on four different CXR data sets for tuberculosis, pneumonia, and COVID-19, achieving a maximum average F1-score between 96.39% and 100%.

3.7 Deep Learning for Chest X-ray Images Localization

Deep learning (DL) approaches have continued to achieve promising results for CXR image localization. CXR classification and localisation are two interconnected tasks. CXR classification aims to classify a given CXR image into different predefined classes, typically referring to specific pathologies, whereas localisation focuses on identifying the regions of interest (ROIs) within the CXR image that refer to specific abnormalities. Accurate localisation can help in establishing trust to a DL model as it can enhance its interpretability, thus potentially enabling its use in clinical practice. Zhou et al. [308] introduced the concept of Class Activation Mapping (CAM) for localising ROIs in an image. CAM provides a way to generate heat-maps that highlight the discriminative regions contributing to the classification decision, providing insights into the ROIs for abnormality detection. By applying a thresholding technique to separate ROIs, the localised regions are extracted, providing a visual explanation of the areas that significantly contribute to the target class predicted by a CNN model [85, 233].

A number of distinct architectures, including YOLO, Mask R-CNN, and quicker R-CNN, have been developed in recent years in computer vision research with the goal of creating quicker and more accurate algorithms for localization tasks Zhao et al. [306]. These cutting-edge designs have been quickly modified for CXR analysis and have demonstrated to deliver high-level performance. As an illustration, Park et al. [194] research showed that the (original) YOLO architecture was effective at locating pneumothorax on chest radiographs. The model was assessed using CXRs from patients who had percutaneous transthoracic needle biopsy (PTNB) for pulmonary lesions. In several works (Hwang et al. [114]; Cha et al. [43]), classification architectures (like ResNet, DenseNet, etc.) were modified to directly regress landmark positions for CXR localization tasks. To address this, it is common practise to modify the networks to provide heatmap forecasts and draw boxes around the regions that produced the strongest signals. For each of the four different forms of CXR anomalies, Hwang et al. [114] customised a DenseNet-based classifier to generate heatmap predictions. Pixel-wise cross entropy between the predictions and annotations was used to train the network. The ResNet-50 and ResNet-101 architectures were similarly modified by Cha et al. [43] for the localisation of nodules and masses on the CXR.

Rajpurkar et al.'s [210] CheXNet DL model achieved performance comparable to expert radiologists in pneumonia diagnosis. Despite focusing on classification, the model implicitly learns to identify and localise pneumonia regions within CXR images. Wang et al. [280]

showed that a combined weakly supervised multi-label image classification and disease localisation framework is capable of detecting and even spatially localising thoracic diseases by using the activation and weights acquired from the network. Li et al. [151] proposed a unified classification and localisation approach that leverages both class information and limited location annotation by first using a CNN to process the input image, and then divide the image into a grid of patches to capture the local information specific to the disease. Han et al. [99] proposed a Radiomics-Guided Transformer (RGT) model that combines global image information with local radiomics-guided auxiliary data for accurate pathology localisation and classification without requiring bounding box annotations. RGT consists of image and radiomics Transformer branches, fusion layers for aggregating information, and cross-attention layers for interaction between image and radiomics features. In another work, Ouyang et al. [190] introduced a novel attention-driven weakly supervised algorithm that combines activation- and gradient-based visual attention through a hierarchical attention mining framework.

3.8 Lung ultrasound Images

Lung ultrasound is a well known medical imaging technique for the detection of pneumonia and related lung sicknesses [191]. As an alternative to CT and X-ray, lung ultrasound (LUS) is a portable, cheap, non-invasive, and easy-to-use medical imaging technology that can be used to identify lung illnesses [174]. In addition, LUS imaging is an effective technique for early diagnosis and follow-up of COVID-19 patients, according to recent medical literature [81, 196, 266]. Fiala et al. [81] provide a succinct summary of LUS results in COVID-19 patients.

3.9 Deep Learning for Lung Ultra Sound Images Classification and Detection

Diaz-Escobar et al. [71] classified the POCUS LUS dataset [38] using binary (COVID-19 vs. pneumonia and COVID-19 vs. healthy) and three-class (COVID-19, pneumonia, and healthy) pre-trained deep learning (DL) models, such as VGG19 [244], InceptionV3 [257], Xception [52], and ResNet50 [100]. Their findings demonstrated that InceptionV3 achieved the highest AUC of 0.97 for distinguishing COVID-19 cases from healthy controls and patients with pneumonia. A lightweight DL design for COVID-19 LUS diagnosis was proposed by Awasthi et al. [18]. The newly developed technique, known as Mini-CovidNet, alters MobileNet with focus loss, achieving an accuracy of 0.83 on the POCUS dataset. Che et al. [49] evaluated a dataset made up of both the POCUS [38] and ICLUS-DB [247] datasets, using a multi-scale residual CNN with a feature fusion approach, achieving an average accuracy of 0.95. Horry et al. [108] conducted an experiment on US images of COVID-19, normal and bacterial pneumonia, by applying transfer learning for the classification approach using eight CNN-based models, achieving a recall and precision of 1.0. Similarly, Roberts et al. [216] carried out a study on classifying COVID-19, bacterial pneumonia, and normal cases on the POCUS dataset [38] by applying DL techniques using the VGG16 [244] and ResNet18 [100] architectures, achieving an accuracy of 0.86 and an AUC of 0.90. Sadik et al. [222] also experimented on the POCUS dataset using four DL models (DenseNet201 [112], ResNet152V2 [100], Xception [52], and VGG19 [244]), achieving an accuracy of 0.91 and an F1-score of 0.90. Zheng et al. [307] proposed a multi-modal approach that combines imaging and text data using a neural network that can classify COVID-19 vs. non-COVID-19 cases, achieving an accuracy of 0.98 and a F1-score of 0.99. It must be noted that in many research works that focused on COVID-19 detection using DL approaches, multi-modal approaches have proven to be more effective, achieving better classification performance than methods relying on a single modality [108, 110, 307].

3.10 Metrics for Medical Imaging System Evaluation

Essential performance criteria, comprising accuracy, F1-score, precision, recall, sensitivity, specificity, and dice coefficient, are used to evaluate a typical medical image processing system. These measurements are computed mathematically.

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (3.1)$$

$$F1_{score} = 2 \times \frac{Precision \times Recall}{Precision + Recall} \quad (3.2)$$

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (3.3)$$

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (3.4)$$

$$IoU = \frac{A \cap B}{A \cup B} \quad (3.5)$$

$$AUC \approx \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \frac{(FPR_{i+1} - FPR_i) \times (TPR_{i+1} + TPR_i)}{2} \quad (3.6)$$

Where:

- FPR_i and FPR_{i+1} are the False Positive Rates at points i and $i + 1$ respectively.
- TPR_i and TPR_{i+1} are the True Positive Rates at points i and $i + 1$ respectively.
- The sum is taken over all points of the ROC curve (from 1 to $N - 1$).

3.11 Summary

This chapter provided a thorough overview of various methods and current research techniques in solving medical image classification and detection problems. The generic structure that the majority of CAD systems have used for the past years, impact of the research has been discussed together with the recommended methodologies and framework. The approaches and frameworks that have proven successful in addressing the complex problems presented by medical image analysis are also highlighted in these sections. This explanation of suggested methods is designed to direct aspiring researchers and professionals in their search for efficient solutions. This section thoughtfully discussed the important and challenging problems that are deeply entwined with the field of medical image analysis. By identifying these key elements, the discourse emphasises how they directly affect the development of this important field, raising awareness of the complex issues that must be handled.

Additionally, this chapter also goes beyond simply reviewing current methods but introducing a number of cutting-edge and fascinating techniques. These cutting-edge developments have the innate potential to advance the development of medical image analysis by presenting fresh opportunities for investigation and research.

Chapter 4

Multi-modal lung ultrasound image classification by fusing image-based features and probe information

The use of biomedical imaging methods (e.g. US, X-ray, CT) has recently shown potential in the detection of COVID-19, allowing in most cases for faster diagnosis than with the widely used RT-PCR approach [108, 187]. Furthermore, deep learning methods and more specifically convolutional neural networks (CNNs), have demonstrated high efficiency in many computer vision-oriented tasks, including the classification and segmentation of images, as well as object detection [150]. Consequently, research on AI/machine learning systems has extensively focused on automating image analysis in the clinical field [154], and deep learning-based automated detection of COVID-19 using LUS imaging has been shown to achieve high performance [37, 38, 219].

Despite numerous research works on automated LUS image classification, the performance achieved is not yet on par with the level required for real-world clinical practice. To this end, in this work, this research employed a large lung ultrasound image dataset (COVIDx-US [75]) that contains 22,776 LUS images, obtained using a linear or convex US probe, and characterised as referring to COVID-19, pneumonia, other pathologies, or normal images. This research proposed a multi-modal approach for LUS image classification that fuses image-based features, extracted using common CNN models pre-trained on ImageNet [69], with information about the probe used to obtain the input LUS image. The proposed approach was evaluated on the examined dataset against commonly used pre-trained CNN models, demonstrating a consistent improvement in performance against all the examined models.

The contribution of this work can be summarised as follows: (i) This research evaluates the performance of several well-proven CNN architectures that have been shown to perform well on general image classification tasks, and examine them on the task of classifying LUS images as belonging to COVID-19, normal, pneumonia, and others. (ii) This research proposed a multi-modal approach where image-based features extracted by the CNN models are combined with information about the type of probe used in order to acquire the ultrasound image, in order to enhance the final classification performance. (iii) This research provided detailed performance evaluation of the proposed multi-modal architecture on the examined LUS image dataset.

4.1 Research Methodology

This research attempted to improve the performance of common pre-trained CNN models on the task of classifying lung ultrasound images as COVID-19, pneumonia, other lung diseases/conditions, or normal. To this end, this research proposed and evaluated a multi-modal approach where image-based features extracted by the CNN models are combined with information about the type of probe used in order to acquire the ultrasound image, in

FIGURE 4.1: Example US images from the COVIDx-US dataset for each class and probe type. (a-d) linear probe, (e-h) convex probe.

order to enhance the final classification performance. The proposed models were trained and evaluated on a dataset containing 22,776 lung ultrasound images.

4.1.1 Dataset

The COVIDx-US [75] (version 1.5) collection is heterogeneous in nature and includes lung ultrasonic imaging data from numerous sources with different properties, such as different US probe types (convex or linear), symptoms exhibited by the patients, demographic information, and others. It contains 220 lung ultrasound videos created using linear or convex probes, from which 22,776 processed ultrasound images are extracted. The ultrasound videos in the dataset were acquired from nine different sources: 1) ButterflyNetwork, 2) GrepMed, 3) LITFL, 4) The PocusAtlas, 5) Radiopaedia, 6) CoreUltrasound, 7) University of Florida (UF), 8) Scientific Publications, and 9) Clarius. In the current COVIDx-US version, US images are divided into four categories: “COVID-19”, “normal”, “pneumonia”, and “other”. The dataset contains 9,227 US images categorised as “COVID-19”, 2,245 categorised as “normal”, 4,300 as “pneumonia”, and 7,004 as “other”. In the absence of an official training/test split, this research opted to split the dataset into 90% training and 10% test, using random stratified sampling in order to preserve the classes distribution. The images in the training set were further divided into 80% for training and 20% for validation in order to facilitate the training of the machine learning models. Apart from the class that it belongs to, each image was also annotated with the type of US probe (linear or convex) used for its acquisition. Linear probes have a flat array and look, producing pictures with a better resolution but less tissue penetration, whereas convex probes (or curved linear probes) have a curved array with a wider field of view at a lower frequency, offering wider depth and deeper penetration [175]. Examples of LUS images from the COVIDx-US dataset for each class and probe type are shown in Figure 4.1.

4.1.2 Proposed architecture

Preliminary experimentation on the examined dataset using various established CNN models, pre-trained on ImageNet and fine-tuned on the training set of the dataset, demonstrated that such an approach can achieve impressive performance, with accuracies and F1-scores up to 96.5%. Nevertheless, as explained in the description of the dataset, the COVIDx-US dataset contains LUS images acquired using a linear or a convex probe. LUS images acquired with different types of probes exhibit some different characteristics, as can be seen in Figure 4.1. As a result, and despite the high performance achieved during our preliminary experimentation, this research hypothesises that the presence in the dataset of US images obtained using various types of probes (linear, convex) may hinder the ability of the machine learning model to precisely classify a US image. Dividing the dataset into LUS images acquired using a linear probe and images acquired using a convex probe could be a potential

FIGURE 4.2: Outline of the proposed architecture.

solution to this issue. However, this would lead to: (a) a reduction in the number of training samples, (b) the requirement for creating and training two separate machine learning models, one for images acquired using a linear probe, and one for images acquired using a convex probe, resulting in reduced practicality and increased computational cost, and (c) potential reduction in the generalisation ability of the trained models, since the high accuracy and F1-score achieved during the preliminary experimentation demonstrated that despite their differences, images acquired with these two types of probes exhibit similar features that can be successfully extracted using a single machine learning model.

To address this issue and avoid dividing the dataset according to probe type, thus having to train two separate models, this research proposed a multi-modal approach where features extracted using a CNN model, pre-trained on ImageNet, are fused with information about the type of probe used to acquire the input image. An outline of the proposed approach is provided in Figure 4.2. The proposed deep learning approach consists of a neural network with two branches. The first branch takes a LUS image as an input and passes it through the convolutional base of a pre-trained CNN, i.e. the convolutional layers without the final fully connected layers used for classification. The output of the convolutional layers is then flattened before being fused with the output of the second branch of the neural network. In this work, this research examined the performance of the following nine established CNN models for the first branch of the proposed model: MobileNetV2 [230], InceptionV3 [257], InceptionResNetV2 [256], Xception [52], ResNet50V2 [100], EfficientNetB4 [259], DenseNet121, DenseNet169, DenseNet201 [112].

The second branch of the proposed neural network takes as an input the type of probe used (linear or convex) and maps it to a 1-dimensional embedding of size 512. To compute the probe embedding, the input is first passed through a fully connected (dense) layer of size 1024, followed by another fully connected layer of size 1024, and finally a fully connected layer of size 512. A ReLU activation function is used for all the fully connected layers. To reduce overfitting and improve the generalisation ability of the model, a dropout layer [250] with a dropout rate of 0.4 is added after each of the first two fully connected layers, as shown in Figure 4.2. The output of both branches is then concatenated and passed through a fully connected layer of size 4 (equal to the number of classes in the dataset) that uses a softmax activation function for the final classification of the input image.

4.1.3 Training and classification

To evaluate the efficiency of the proposed multi-modal approach, this research compared its performance (see Section 4.2) to the performance of the base CNNs used, fine-tuned on the examined dataset. All base CNN models used were pre-trained on ImageNet and the Keras library was used for both the pre-trained models, as well as for implementing the proposed architecture. Both the proposed and the baseline models were trained using the Adam optimiser, a learning rate of 0.0001, a batch size of 16, and sparse categorical cross-entropy as the loss function. In addition, the training process stopped after 20 epochs with no improvement in validation accuracy, and the learning rate was multiplied by a factor of 0.2 after 2 epochs with no improvement, with a lower bound on the learning rate of 10^{-6} .

TABLE 4.1: Classification performance (%) of the baseline and the proposed methods for various base CNN models. Results in bold indicate the best performance for each metric and approach. Underlined results indicate the overall best performance.

Base CNN	Base CNN					Base CNN + Probe info (proposed)				
	Params.	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1	Params.	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1
MobileNetV2	2,508,868	96.73	96.51	96.46	96.49	4,087,364	99.32	99.14	99.42	99.27
InceptionV3	22,007,588	96.49	96.45	96.67	96.55	23,586,084	99.34	99.18	99.39	99.28
InceptionResNetV2	54,490,340	96.44	96.28	95.80	96.03	56,068,836	99.39	99.23	99.46	99.36
Xception	21,262,892	94.38	95.03	95.24	95.11	22,841,388	99.98	99.99	99.94	99.97
ResNet50V2	23,966,212	96.57	96.32	96.35	96.33	25,544,708	99.71	99.70	99.70	99.70
EfficientNetB4	18,025,052	96.81	96.47	96.70	96.58	19,603,548	99.41	99.24	99.22	99.37
DenseNet121	7,238,212	96.53	96.30	96.18	96.24	8,816,708	99.34	99.18	99.39	99.28
DenseNet169	12,969,028	96.75	96.48	96.58	96.53	14,547,524	99.36	99.17	99.49	99.30
DenseNet201	18,698,308	96.49	96.35	96.10	96.22	20,276,804	99.36	99.14	99.41	99.30
Mean		96.35	96.24	96.23	96.23		99.47	99.33	99.49	99.43
St. Dev.		0.75	0.46	0.47	0.46		0.23	0.30	0.21	0.24

Xception + Probe info (proposed)

Predicted

		Normal	COVID-19	Pneumonia	Other
Actual	Normal	448	1	0	0
	COVID-19	0	1845	0	0
	Pneumonia	0	0	860	0
	Other	0	0	0	1400

EfficientNetB4

Predicted

		Normal	COVID-19	Pneumonia	Other
Actual	Normal	448	1	0	0
	COVID-19	2	1843	0	0
	Pneumonia	0	0	799	61
	Other	0	0	81	1319

FIGURE 4.3: Confusion matrices for the best performing proposed model (Xception + Probe information) and the best performing base CNN model (EfficientNetB4).

4.2 Results & Discussion

The proposed approach using the nine base CNN models, as well as the nine base CNN models individually, were trained and evaluated on the COVIDx-US dataset for the task of classifying LUS images into “COVID-19”, “Normal”, “Pneumonia”, and “Other” (4-class problem). Classification performance was measured using the following metrics: classification accuracy, precision, recall (sensitivity), and F1-score. Furthermore, since precision, recall, and F1-score depend on the class that is considered as positive, they were computed for all classes separately and the average across the four classes was reported as the final metric value. It must be noted that all experiments were carried out using the TensorFlow library, the Keras API, and the Python programming language on a Tesla K40c and a GeForce GTX Titan GPU. Additionally, all LUS images were resized to 224×224 pixels before being fed as input to the examined models.

4.2.1 Experimental results

The classification performance achieved using the baseline and the proposed approaches is reported in Table 4.1, in terms of the classification accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score metrics. From this table, it is evident that the fusion of the probe information and the image-based CNN features consistently led to an improvement in all classification metrics over the baseline CNN approach. The overall best performing model was the proposed “Xception + Probe information” that achieved an F1-score of 99.97%, an accuracy of 99.98%, a precision of 99.99%, and a recall of 99.94%, miss-classifying only one LUS image, as shown in Figure 4.3. The proposed approach outperformed the baseline approach regardless of the base CNN model used, with the worst performing model, i.e. “MobileNetV2 + Probe information”, achieving a higher F1-score compared to the best performing baseline model, i.e. EfficientNetB4, (99.27% vs. 96.58%). Among the baseline models, EfficientNetB4 achieved the best classification performance, with a classification accuracy of 96.81%, F1-score of 96.58%, precision of 96.47%, and recall of 96.70%. The confusion matrix for the EfficientNetB4 baseline model is depicted in Figure 4.3. It is worth mentioning that although EfficientNetB4 achieved the best performance among the baseline models in terms of accuracy, F1-score, and recall, MobileNetV2 achieved a marginally higher precision (96.51% vs. 96.47%), although such a difference can be considered as negligible. The difference in classification metrics between the baseline and the proposed models is presented in Table 4.2, whereas the confusion matrices for the best performing proposed and baseline models are depicted in Figure 4.3.

4.2.2 Comparison to state of the art

In a recent work that used the examined COVIDx-US dataset, Adedigba et al. [2] reported a classification accuracy of 99.74% using MobileNetV2 [230] and 99.75% using SqueezeNet [115]. However, this work was conducted on a previous version of the dataset that contained a total of 174 LUS videos, compared to 220 contained in the current version (Version 1.5) that is used in this work. Furthermore and most importantly, in their work, Adedigba et al. [2] opted to simplify the examined 4-class problem and focus on the COVID-19 vs. Non-COVID-19 problem by grouping together all images that did not belong to the COVID-19 class and annotating them as Non-COVID-19. Consequently, the reported accuracy refers to the aforementioned binary classification problem. To evaluate our proposed approach and provide a fair evaluation against the Adedigba et al. [2] approach, this research first replicated their experiment using the current version of the COVIDx-US dataset. Classification performance for the COVID-19 vs. Non-COVID-19 binary problem was indeed consistent with the one reported by Adedigba et al. [2]. However, when examined on the 4-class problem, the accuracy of the MobileNetV2 model dropped to 96.73%, as shown in Table 4.1, whereas the proposed approach using MobileNetV2 as its base CNN achieved an enhanced classification accuracy of 99.32%.

4.2.3 Additional Discussion

It is clear from Table 4.1 and Table 4.2 that for each of the base models under consideration, the proposed technique outperformed the baseline approach in terms of all performance metrics. In addition, regardless of the base CNN model utilised, the proposed approach consistently offered better classification performance in terms of all the metrics. As shown in Table 4.2, the introduction of the US probe information led to an average increase of +3.11% (± 0.90) in accuracy, +3.09% (± 0.69) in precision, +3.26% (± 0.61) in recall, and +3.19% (± 0.63) in F1-score for all the baseline CNN models. The results achieved for both the proposed and the baseline approach are quite stable, with the proposed models achieving an F1-score between 99.27%, using MobileNetV2 as the base CNN, and 99.97% using Xception as the base CNN, compared to the baseline models that achieved an F1-score between 95.11% for Xception and 96.58% for EfficientNetB4. The stability of the examined models is also evidenced by the low standard deviations computed across all models for all the examined performance metrics, as shown in the last row of Table 4.1.

TABLE 4.2: Difference (Δ) between the metrics' values achieved for the proposed method and the base CNN method.

Base CNN	Δ	Δ	Δ	Δ
	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1
MobileNetV2	2.59	2.63	2.96	2.78
InceptionV3	2.85	2.73	2.72	2.73
InceptionResNetV2	2.95	2.95	3.66	3.33
Xception	5.60	4.96	4.70	4.86
ResNet50V2	3.14	3.38	3.35	3.37
EfficientNetB4	2.60	2.77	2.52	2.79
DenseNet121	2.81	2.88	3.21	3.04
DenseNet169	2.61	2.69	2.91	2.77
DenseNet201	2.87	2.79	3.31	3.08
Mean	3.11	3.09	3.26	3.19
St. Dev.	0.90	0.69	0.61	0.63

FIGURE 4.4: F1-score (%) achieved for the proposed and the baseline models in relation to the number of parameters of each model.

Considering the above, as well as the presented results, it is evident that the proposed multi-modal method of combining LUS image-based CNN features with information about the US probe type used to acquire the input LUS image can outperform models that rely solely on pre-trained CNN models for classifying LUS images into “COVID-19”, “Normal”, “Pneumonia”, and “Other” (4-class problem). Furthermore, despite the proposed model based on the Xception CNN model achieving the best classification performance, it is evident from Table 4.1 that all models performed considerably well, thus providing the flexibility to the user to decide on the model to be used based on its computational complexity, by selecting the model with the lowest amount of parameters that achieves an acceptable performance, as shown in Figure 4.4.

4.3 Summary

This research proposed a multi-modal approach for the classification of lung ultrasound images for the task of distinguishing them between “COVID-19”, “Normal”, “Pneumonia”, and “Other (lung diseases/conditions)”. The proposed approach relies on the fusion of image-based CNN features with information regarding the type of ultrasound probe (linear

or convex) used to acquire the input image. Experimental results on a large lung ultrasound image dataset containing 22,776 lung ultrasound images demonstrated the superiority of the proposed approach compared to solely using the base CNN model for the classification of the images. The highest classification accuracy of 99.98% and highest F1-score of 99.97% were achieved using the proposed combination of probe information with the pre-trained Xception CNN model, compared to the highest accuracy of 96.81% and highest F1-score of 96.58% achieved using solely the EfficientNetB4 pre-trained CNN model. The next chapter focused on examining similar state of the art algorithms for detecting Covid-19 on Chest X-ray images. Chest X-ray scan is the most popular radiological examination, which is carried out widely in healthcare facilities, including clinics and hospitals. It is used to check the chest region for diagnosis of conditions like lung infections and heart problems. Also the Chest X-ray open source datasets are more available and accessible for machine learning applications for medical image analysis than ultra sound images.

Chapter 5

On the Use of Deep Learning for Imaging-based COVID-19 Detection Using Chest X-rays

The 2019 novel corona virus (COVID-19) pandemic that was first reported in Wuhan, China in December 2019 became a public health issue around the world [218]. The infection that caused the COVID-19 pandemic was called a Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome, also known as SARS-CoV-2 [251]. As of the second quarter of 2021, the COVID-19 pandemic keeps on affecting the well-being and health of the general public. A critical step in the battle against COVID-19 is a reliable and effective detection method for diagnosing infected patients, with the end-goal of prompt treatment and care. Corona viruses are a huge group of viruses that cause illness. Examples are the Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS-CoV), the Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS-CoV) and COVID-19. COVID-19's earliest symptoms include, fever, cough, fatigue or myalgia. [94, 107, 293].

The main screening technique used for identifying COVID-19 cases is reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction testing (RT-PCR) [278, 290], which can recognise SARS-CoV-2 RNA from respiratory samples gathered through various means, e.g. nasopharyngeal or oropharyngeal swabs. Initial findings have stated that the RT-PCR testing shows relatively poor sensitivity [79]. Further findings showed that RT-PCR testing is highly specific and the probability of false positives is low. However, the amount of virus in a swab varies between patients, so at initial test it can provide a true negative result that turns out to be false negative in the late stage, which is dangerous [281, 285]. A screening method that can additionally be used for COVID-19 detection is radiography assessment, where chest radiography imaging such as computed tomography (CT) or chest X-ray (CXR) is conducted and analysed by radiologists to search for visual markers related with SARS-CoV-2 viral infection. Early investigations showed that patients present abnormalities in chest radiography images that pointed out features of those with COVID-19 [111, 182], with some recommending that radiography assessment could be utilised as a primary tool for diagnosing COVID-19 [5]. However, the American College of Radiology (ACR) [10] and the World Health Organisation (WHO) [6] are sceptical and urge caution in using chest X-rays or chest CT scans as a primary diagnostic tool for COVID-19, with the WHO suggesting the use of chest imaging if RT-PCR is not available at all or in a timely manner.

Studies have shown that patients with COVID-19 exhibit some characteristics on their chest X-rays: It primarily affects the peripheral and lower areas of the lungs, nodular shadowing, ground glass opacity, and accumulations of fluid and tissue in pulmonary alveoli, which is also called consolidation [14, 51]. An important observation made during a study of COVID-19-related imaging diagnosis is that initial symptoms are not visible at all or are slightly visible on chest X-rays within the first 3 days since symptom onset but are very obvious after 10 to 12 days. A common complication of influenza-like illnesses is viral pneumonia, which has been shown to also be a complication of COVID-19 [103]. Medical imaging, specifically chest computed tomography (CT) and chest X-ray, is frequently utilised as an integrated assessment in the detection and management of pneumonia. However, given that viral pneumonia can be a complication of various illnesses, it is important to be able to assess whether a specific case is related to COVID-19.

The required medical and clinical resources for COVID-19 diagnosis at a global scale are a major challenge. Several countries are unable to carry out large numbers of COVID-19 tests [155], because of limited diagnosis tools. There is a need to identify a quick and reliable tool that can detect COVID-19 effectively with minimal effort. Numerous attempts have been conducted for devising an appropriate and quick approach to recognise infected patients in an early stage. In the wake of taking chest CT scans of 21 patients with COVID-19 in China, Guan et al. [93] found that CT scan analysis showed reciprocal pulmonary parenchymal abnormalities and pneumonic consolidation and a fringe lung distribution. Thus, the analysis effectively extracted the main features of the virus.

All things considered, radiography assessment is quicker and has more prominent accessibility than RT-PCR testing, given the availability of chest radiology imaging systems in the healthcare sector. In addition, the turnaround time for X-ray examination is approximately 5.08 hours [8]. Chest X-ray imaging is frequently used as a standard testing technique for respiratory complaint [178] and is easily accessible, making it a suitable COVID-19 detection method. Nevertheless, considering that COVID-19 symptoms are not visible in X-rays during the first days of the infection [288], chest X-ray imaging cannot fully replace RT-PCR but can play an important role in patient screening for indicating potential COVID-19 cases, especially when RT-PCR is not easily accessible. However, probably the greatest bottleneck confronted is the requirement for expert radiologists to decipher the radiography images since the visual pointers can be unobtrusive. Consequently, computer diagnostic frameworks that can help radiologists to quickly and precisely decipher radiography images to recognise COVID-19 cases are of critical importance for an accessible-to-all fight against the virus.

The critical need to develop solutions to help curb the challenges in the fight against COVID-19, motivated by the availability of CT and chest X-ray images of COVID-19 cases, has led this study to carry out experiments on deep convolutional neural network (CNN) architectures which can effectively detect COVID-19 with the highest accuracy. To this end, this research opted to select eleven well-established CNN architectures that have been shown to be efficient in various image classification tasks, and conduct a comparative study to examine their performance for the task of classifying chest X-ray images as belonging to healthy individuals, individuals with COVID-19, or individuals with non-COVID-19-related viral pneumonia. Three different versions of the examined CNN architectures were evaluated: (1) a baseline version where the pre-trained CNN models were used as is, changing only the classifier in their output to suit the task at hand, (2) a modified version with two additional fully connected layers between the convolutional base and the classifier, and dropout layers before each fully connected layer, and (3) a modified version with two larger fully connected layers between the convolutional base and the classifier, and batch normalisation and Leaky ReLU layers before each fully connected layer. All the examined approaches were trained and evaluated on a data set with real chest X-ray images using a stratified 5-fold cross validation procedure, while the best performing model was also evaluated on a completely unseen data set. Supervised classification experiments demonstrated the efficiency of the proposed approach, reaching a highest classification accuracy of 98.04% and a highest F1-score of 98.22% for the best performing setting.

The novelty of this work can be summarised as follows: (a) This research provided a comparative study of the performance of multiple well-established CNN architectures that have been proven to work well on generic image classification tasks, and examine them on the task of classifying chest X-ray images as belonging to healthy individuals, individuals with COVID-19, or individuals with non-COVID-19-related viral pneumonia. (b) This research proposed two different adjustments of these architectures and examine how classification performance is affected on the examined task. (c) This research examined the performance of the used models when using weights pre-trained on ImageNet without any additional training and when end-to-end training is applied. (d) This research show that although the pre-trained CNN models have been proven to be very efficient on generic image classification tasks (e.g. ImageNet), performance suffers when fine-tuned for chest x-ray image classification, but minor extensions of the architectures, such as the ones proposed in this work, allow these CNN architectures to perform exceptionally well on the task, while also exploiting the available pre-trained weights, thus reducing the amount of x-ray images needed for training the models. (e) Finally, similar available works in the literature commonly evaluate

the performance of the proposed models by dividing their data set into a training set and a test set. However, due to the limited availability of COVID-19-related images, such data sets are typically created by combining multiple data sets, which can lead to the trained neural networks learning features that are specific of the data set more than the ones that are specific of the disease, thus leading to overfitting and reduced generalisation ability [167]. To ensure that the models proposed in this work do not suffer from this issue, in addition to our test set, this research evaluated the performance of our models on a completely independent data set, without any additional training or fine-tuning.

5.1 Research Methodology

This research examined various deep neural network architectures for the task of classifying chest X-ray images as belonging to healthy individuals, individuals with COVID-19, or individuals with viral pneumonia (not COVID-19-related), and proposed three different adjustments to the architectures that led to increased performance for the task at hand. This research opted to include viral pneumonia cases that are not related to COVID-19 as the third class in our experiments, since viral pneumonia is a complication of various diseases but has been shown to also be a complication of COVID-19 [103]. The performance of the proposed approaches was evaluated on a publicly available chest X-ray image data set [55], demonstrating their efficiency in improving COVID-19 detection regardless the base network architecture used.

5.1.1 Data set

The COVID-19 radiography database [55] was selected for this work. This database was compiled by a team of researchers from the University of Doha in Qatar and the University of Dhaka in Bangladesh, who collaborated with medical doctors from Pakistan and Malaysia to create a database of chest X-ray images for COVID-19 positive cases along with normal and viral pneumonia images. The database consists of 2905 chest X-ray images, including 219 COVID-19 positive images, 1341 normal images and 1345 viral pneumonia images. The images in the COVID-19 radiography database were sourced from various sources, including the Italian Society of Medical and Interventional Radiology (SIRM) COVID-19 database [118], Cohen et al.'s COVID-19 image data collection [65], the ChestX-ray8 database [280], the Kermany et al. [132] pneumonia chest X-ray images data set, as well as some online repositories [55] where physicians and researchers uploaded COVID-19-related chest X-ray images. All the images are stored in Portable Network Graphics (PNG) file format (24-bit RGB), with a resolution of 1024×1024 pixels. Figure 5.1 depicts sample images from the database for COVID-19, normal and viral pneumonia chest X-ray images.

(a) Normal, (b) COVID-19, (c) Viral pneumonia.

FIGURE 5.1: Sample X-ray images.

5.1.2 Application of data augmentation

One of the obstacles when attempting to apply deep learning techniques for solving a problem is the lack of sufficiently large amounts of data for training the deep learning models. Depending on the application and field, acquiring more data can be very arduous and costly, both in terms of time and resources. Data augmentation, i.e. increasing the amount of available data without gathering new data by applying various operations on the available data, has proven to be effective in image classification [199]. The technique has been used in the ImageNet classifier challenge that won the competition [100, 142], and its widely used by researchers to increase the training data, thereby avoiding over-fitting [289].

This research opted to use data augmentation techniques because of the limited number of images in the COVID-19 radiography database, especially for the COVID-19 class which contained only 219 samples. To achieve this, the images in the training set at each training fold of the cross-validation procedure were used to create additional images by: randomly flipping them horizontally, randomly flipping them vertically, rotating at a random angle between -90 and 90 degrees, randomly shifting across the width by 10% of total width, randomly shifting across the height by 10% of total height, randomly zooming within a range of 0.9 to 1.1, randomly shearing in counter-clockwise direction by an angle of 0 to 0.1 radians, randomly shifting the brightness between 0.5 and 1.5, and finally rescaling by a factor of $1/255$. All pixels outside the boundaries of the input were filled using the nearest neighbour approach.

It must also be noted that all random values for the data augmentation operations were generated using a uniform probability distribution, and that the Keras ImageDataGenerator class was used for the real-time creation of batches of augmented images during each training procedure. By using this data augmentation technique, the number of images in the training set was significantly increased, allowing the efficient use of deep learning techniques by training the machine learning models using a much larger amount of training images. Furthermore, it must be noted that the augmented images were only used for training the models and not for testing, thus only original images from the data set were used for testing the trained models.

5.1.3 Classification using deep neural networks

Considering the limited amount of available images for the task at hand, this research opted to base our approach on established architectures that have been proven to be efficient feature extractors for object detection applications and have been trained using sufficiently large image data sets. To this end, this research selected eleven well established CNN architectures that have achieved state-of-the-art results and were pre-trained on the ImageNet [221] data set, which consists of 1.4 million labelled images with 1000 classes. The selected deep learning models are very popular and widely used in computer vision tasks and have proven to excel in image classification problems. The following deep convolutional neural networks were examined for the task of classifying between COVID-19, normal and viral pneumonia X-ray images (3-class problem): EfficientNetB4 [259], EfficientNetB7 [259], VGG16 [244], Xception [52], InceptionResNetV2 [256], InceptionV3 [257], MobileNetV2 [230], ResNet50V2 [100], DenseNet121, DenseNet169 and DenseNet201 [112]. The three following different approaches were used for adjusting these architectures to the examined task, which were all trained using the Adam optimiser, a batch size of 16 and a learning rate of 0.0001. Furthermore, Cross-Entropy was used as the loss function, computed as $L_{CE} = -\sum_{c=1}^M y_{o,c} \log(p_{o,c})$, with $M = 3$ the number of classes, $y_{o,c}$ a binary indicator (0 or 1) if observation o belongs to class c , and $p_{o,c}$ the predicted probability that observation o is of class c .

To train a robust CNN that will accurately classify images, hyperparameters must be tuned according to the examined problem. Our choice of hyperparameters was made after some preliminary experimentation and by following the conclusions of the Kandel et al. [129] study on the effect of batch size and learning rate when the Adam optimiser is used for training CNNs for medical image classification, which recommended that decreasing the batch size and lowering the learning rate will allow the network to train better and generalise more accurately.

It must also be noted that Keras and TensorFlow 2 were used for all the experiments, thus all pre-trained networks used in this work refer to the respective Keras implementations. Detailed diagrams of the proposed neural network architectures are depicted in Figure 5.2.

Baseline approach

The pre-trained models were used as a feature extractor. CNNs are made up of two parts, which are the convolutional base and the classifier. The convolutional base contains the convolutional and pooling layers that extract features from images. The classifier part is composed of a fully connected layer (softmax) with the goal of classifying images based on detected features. The concept of the baseline approach is to make use of only the convolutional base (feature extractor) without the classifier and feed its output directly into a softmax activated layer [153] with 3 neurons (Figure 5.2a), corresponding to the number of the targeted classes (COVID-19, normal, viral pneumonia). The convolutional base layer was set to freeze, in order to take advantage of the features learned by the models trained on the ImageNet data set, therefore the weights of the pre-trained network were not updated during training. Then, the new classifier was trained for determining one of the three available classes given the set of extracted features [53]. It must be noted that contrary to the other examined architectures, VGG16 contains two fully connected layers before the final classifier. This research opted to keep these layers in the VGG16 baseline model in order to be consistent with changing only the final softmax activated layer for all the examined architectures.

Approach 1

The used deep learning classification approach is called round off fine tuning of the entire model. As shown in (Figure 5.2b), for Approach 1, this research added a new classifier with a new mini network of two small fully connected layers that fits our own purpose. The first fully connected layer has 128 neurons while the second has 64 neurons followed by a Softmax classifier with 3 neurons corresponding to our 3 output classes. This research also added a global average pooling layer after the last convolutional block of the base network and a dropout layer with a rate of 0.3 before each of the two intermediate dense layers, which has been proven to help reduce the risk of overfitting [250]. Then, the pre-trained weights on ImageNet were used as the initialisation of the base network in order to adapt the pre-trained features to the new data.

Approach 2

The second approach is one of the most commonly used fine-tuning methods for image classification.

This research added a new classifier with two fully connected layers. The first fully connected layer has 2048 neurons, while the second has 1024 neurons, followed by a Softmax classifier with 3 neurons corresponding to our 3 output classes. As shown in (Figure 5.2c), this research also added a flatten layer after the output of the convolutional base of the base network and a batch normalisation layer before each of the three dense layers, which has also been proven to help reduce the risk of overfitting and accelerate the learning process [117]. This research also opted to add a leaky ReLU layer after each batch normalisation layer as this has been proven to improve the performance of a network [276]. Then, similar to Approach 1, the pre-trained weights on ImageNet were used as the initialisation of the base network in order to adapt the pre-trained features to the new data.

5.1.4 Hyperparameter settings and added layers

Given the countless choices in numbers, types and parameters of layers, this research opted to examine the performance of as simple architectures as possible, adding only 3 dense layers, and compared between a simpler approach (Approach 1) and a more complex one (Approach 2). The hyperparameters and added layers of the proposed approaches were selected by conducting some preliminary experiments on a smaller data set, as follows: For all approaches, this research opted to use the Adam optimiser, a batch size of 16 and a learning

FIGURE 5.2: Proposed neural network architecture for the (a) Baseline approach, (b) Approach 1, (c) Approach 2.

rate of 0.0001, as these settings performed best in a study carried out by Kandel et al. [129] about the effect of batch size and the impact of learning rates on the performance of CNNs for image classification of medical images. In addition, three fully connected (dense) layers were used after the convolutional layers of the base network for both Approach 1 and 2. In both cases, the second dense layer had half the neurons of the first one, while the third dense layer (output layer) had three neurons corresponding to the three output classes.

For the dropout layers in Approach 1, a dropout rate of 0.3 was used. Dropout was proposed by Hinton et al. [250] as a regulariser which randomly sets a portion of the activations to the fully connected layers to zero during training, leading to improved generalisation ability and largely preventing overfitting [261]. Apart from the dropout layers, global average pooling was used in Approach 1 to generate a feature map from the output of the convolutional layers of the base network. It is a structural regulariser that helps to avoid overfitting in this layer, first proposed by Lin et al. [153].

Batch normalisation was used in Approach 2 for normalising activations in intermediate layers of the architecture, as it has been shown to improve accuracy, reduce the risk of overfitting and speedup the training process of deep neural networks [35]. Furthermore, a flatten layer was used in order to convert the multidimensional output of the convolutional layers of the base network into a one-dimensional vector which can be fed into the fully connected layer [183]. Finally, Approach 2 used Leaky ReLU activation layers ($\alpha = 0.3$), as they have been shown to improve the performance of a network by Wang et al. [276], who compared the performance of three different activation functions.

5.1.5 Label Smoothing

Label smoothing is a regularisation technique that addresses both overfitting and overconfidence problems. It is a simple method that makes a model more robust and enables it to generalise well. When cross-entropy is used as a loss function, the training process aims to minimise $L_{CE} = -\sum_{c=1}^M y_{o,c} \log(p_{o,c})$, where $y_{o,c}$ is a binary indicator (0 or 1) showing whether observation o belongs to class c . In this case, $y_{o,c}$ is considered a hard target as it is either 0 or 1. When label smoothing is used, the targets $y_{o,c}$ are modified as $y_{o,c}^{LS} = y_{o,c}(1 - \alpha) + \frac{\alpha}{M}$, with M being the number of classes and α the label smoothing parameter. Szegedy et al. [257] proposed the label smoothing technique, which improved the performance of the Inception architecture on the ImageNet data set and several other state-of-the-art deep learning classification models have adopted this method since [215, 310]. This research adopted label smoothing to improve the performance of our models by minimising cross-entropy using soft targets instead of hard targets, with a smoothing parameter $\alpha = 0.1$, thus encouraging the model to be less confident and leading to better generalisation.

5.2 Results and Discussion

The performance of the eleven examined deep convolutional neural network models for the 3-class problem (Normal, COVID-19, Viral pneumonia) using the baseline and the other two proposed approaches was evaluated by conducting supervised classification experiments. Approach 1 and Approach 2 models were evaluated twice, once keeping the pre-trained weights of the base networks frozen and only training the additional layers, and once using the pre-trained weights as initialisation and training the networks end-to-end. A stratified 5-fold cross-validation procedure was followed in order to provide a fair estimate of classification performance and avoid over-fitting. To this end, the available images in the COVID-19 radiography database were divided into five groups, respecting the class distribution, and at each fold of the cross-validation procedure, one group was used for test and the rest for training the examined models. This process was repeated until all groups had been used for test and the overall classification performance was computed by averaging the performance across the five folds.

The computed performance metrics were the accuracy, F1-score, precision, and recall. Furthermore, since the F1-score, precision, and recall depend on which class is considered as positive, their reported scores in this work are the average scores between the three examined classes. In addition to these four metrics, the Jaccard index and the Dice coefficient were also computed from the aggregated test groups across the five folds of the 5-fold cross-validation procedure. All experiments were conducted by employing the TensorFlow library and the Keras API, using the Python programming language on the Google Colab Pro platform (Nvidia Tesla T4 and P100 GPU, 24 GB RAM). It must also be noted that the chest X-ray images were resized to 300×300 pixels before being fed as input to the examined network models, since this size was close to the input size they were originally designed for. Given that the examined networks expected different input sizes and to achieve a fair comparison, this research opted to resize the images to a common size that was close to the one expected by the networks, which varied from 224×224 to 456×456 pixels.

5.2.1 Results for the Baseline Approach

The classification performance achieved using the baseline approach and the other two proposed approaches is reported in Table 5.1, 5.2 and 5.3 respectively, in terms of the classification accuracy, F1-score, precision, recall, Jaccard index and Dice coefficient metrics.

Table 5.1 contains results for the Baseline approach, which performed the worst among the examined approaches. The results are quite stable across all the proposed models, with an average F1-score within the range of 76.39%-91.94%. VGG16 performed the best across all metrics, achieving the highest average F1-score of 91.94%, while EfficientNetB7 achieved the lowest average F1-score of 76.39%. The slightly higher performance for the VGG16 architecture compared to the others can be attributed to the additional two fully connected layers before the final softmax activated layer, as explained in Section 5.1.3. Indeed, when performing the same experiment for VGG16 without the two fully connected layers, the F1-score drops to 87.13%.

5.2.2 Results for Approach 1

Results for Approach 1 are reported in Table 5.2. From Table 5.1, 5.2 and 5.3, it is evident that Approach 1 with end-to-end training provided the best performance among the examined approaches, achieving considerably high metric values for all the examined models. In the case of end-to-end training, the EfficientNetB4 and Xception-based models achieved the highest average F1-scores of 98.22% and 98.20% respectively, while the VGG16 and InceptionV3-based models achieved the lowest average F1-scores of 95.39% and 95.76% respectively. On the other hand, the rest of the models, namely EfficientNetB7, ResNet50V2, InceptionResNetV2, MobileNetV2, DenseNet201, DenseNet169 and DenseNet121 based models achieved an average F1-score within the range of 96.66%-97.92%. In the case of using the pre-trained weights for the base network, performance suffered considerably compared to end-to-end training, with ResNet50V2 achieving the best performance across all metrics,

with an F1-score of 90.81%. Comparing the results from Table 5.1 and 5.2, it is evident that the use of Approach 1 led to significant improvement in classification performance.

5.2.3 Results for Approach 2

Table 5.3 contains classification results for Approach 2, which consistently performed slightly worse than Approach 1, as can be seen from Table 5.2 and 5.3. In the case of end-to-end training, similar to Approach 1, performance for Approach 2 is quite stable across the examined models, with an average F1-score within the range of 94.83%-97.27%. The InceptionV3 and Xception models achieved the highest average F1-scores of 97.27% and 97.26% respectively, while VGG16 achieved the lowest F1-score of 94.83%. In the case of using the pre-trained weights for the base network, performance decreased marginally compared to end-to-end training, with DenseNet169 and DenseNet121 achieving a highest F1-score of 96.12% and 96.06% respectively, with VGG16 achieving the lowest F1-score of 89.22%.

TABLE 5.1: Classification performance (%) of the examined deep neural network architectures following the baseline approach.

Base Model	Accuracy	F1-score	Precision	Recall	Jaccard	Dice
EfficientNetB4	87.50	86.32	93.57	81.48	75.93	86.32
EfficientNetB7	83.75	76.39	91.45	70.86	69.40	81.94
VGG16	92.22	91.94	93.97	90.13	83.21	90.84
Xception	86.02	85.26	92.63	80.18	72.59	84.12
InceptionResNetV2	86.51	86.53	91.34	82.79	73.06	84.43
InceptionV3	86.82	84.79	90.73	80.58	72.60	84.12
MobileNetV2	86.68	85.76	91.87	81.33	72.76	84.24
ResNet50V2	89.02	88.90	93.56	85.14	77.11	87.08
DenseNet121	84.27	80.20	93.77	73.65	70.97	83.02
DenseNet169	87.23	86.52	92.84	82.03	74.75	85.55
DenseNet201	86.37	87.13	93.04	82.83	72.75	84.23

Note: Results in bold denote the best performance for each metric.

TABLE 5.2: Classification performance (%) of the examined deep neural network architectures following Approach 1 when using the pre-trained weights for the base network and when training each network end-to-end.

Base model	End-to-end training						Pre-trained base					
	Accuracy	F1-score	Precision	Recall	Jaccard	Dice	Accuracy	F1-score	Precision	Recall	Jaccard	Dice
EfficientNetB4	98.04	98.22	98.52	97.95	96.52	98.23	89.95	88.71	92.86	85.55	80.35	89.10
EfficientNetB7	96.87	96.66	97.10	96.27	93.24	96.50	88.67	85.70	93.11	81.46	78.35	87.86
VGG16	94.77	95.39	96.11	94.84	88.83	94.08	87.57	85.59	89.23	82.86	72.85	84.29
Xception	98.00	98.20	98.58	97.87	95.98	97.95	90.36	90.07	92.29	88.16	79.92	88.84
InceptionResNetV2	97.38	97.35	97.88	96.89	94.17	97.00	89.05	88.76	91.25	86.65	77.51	87.33
InceptionV3	96.18	95.76	96.73	95.07	90.63	95.09	88.98	88.30	91.13	85.90	76.03	86.39
MobileNetV2	96.90	97.00	97.52	96.53	93.09	96.42	89.40	88.44	92.11	85.57	78.66	88.06
ResNet50V2	97.45	97.92	98.20	97.67	94.94	97.41	91.02	90.81	93.43	88.68	81.23	89.64
DenseNet121	97.07	97.46	97.95	97.03	93.83	96.82	88.06	87.28	93.23	83.02	75.66	86.14
DenseNet169	97.49	97.68	97.76	97.63	94.82	97.34	89.71	88.72	92.60	85.64	79.10	88.33
DenseNet201	97.25	97.15	97.60	96.77	93.93	96.87	89.12	88.25	91.63	85.58	78.21	87.77

Note: Results in bold denote the best performance for each metric and approach. Underlined results denote the overall best performance for each metric.

5.2.4 Validation on unseen data set

To further evaluate the generalisation ability of the proposed approach, this research examined the classification performance of our best performing model, i.e. EfficientNetB4-based Approach 1, on an unseen data set without any additional training or fine-tuning. This research used the COVID-19 Image Repository (Version 2.0) [287], which contains 243 chest X-ray images of COVID-19 cases from the Institute for Diagnostic and Interventional Radiology, Hannover Medical School, Hannover, Germany. Considering that the available COVID-19 X-ray data sets are commonly collections of images from various sources, this research selected this data set in order to ensure that no overlap exists between its images and

the images used for training our models. As shown in Table 5.4, the EfficientNetB4-based Approach 1 model was able to correctly classify 234 out of the 243 (96.30%) COVID-19-related images, miss-classifying 7 images as normal (2.88%), and 2 images as viral pneumonia (0.82%). These results on an unseen data set that was not used for training or fine-tuning our model, further demonstrate its efficiency and generalisation ability.

5.2.5 Execution time

Information regarding the size in terms of trainable parameters and the time and number of epochs taken to train the best performing models for the Baseline approach, Approach 1 and 2 with end-to-end training, and Approach 1 and 2 using the frozen pre-trained weights for the base network is provided in Table 5.5. The average execution times were measured using TensorFlow and the Keras API on the Google Colab Pro platform (Nvidia Tesla T4 and P100 GPU, 24 GB RAM), as well as the training parameters described in Section 5.1.3. From Table 5.5, it is evident that the fastest model to train per epoch was VGG16 for the baseline approach (108 s/epoch), followed by the EfficientNetB4 and Xception for Approach 1 with end-to-end training (112 and 111 s/epoch respectively), which also achieved the best overall classification performance. DenseNet169 for Approach 2 using the pre-trained weights for the base network required the most time to train at 166 s/epoch. However, it must be noted that for the sake of consistency and fairness, the training parameters were the same for all the models tested. Consequently, fine tuning the parameters for each specific model could potentially lead to better overall training times for some of the models, and as a result, the execution times and number of epochs required for training that are reported in Table 5.5 must be taken into consideration only under the specific configuration and hardware.

5.2.6 Discussion

From Table 5.1, 5.2, and 5.3, as well as from the Precision-Recall plot in Figure 5.3, it is evident that both Approach 1 and Approach 2 led to improved performance compared to the baseline approach for all the examined base models. Furthermore, Approach 1 consistently provided higher classification performance, in terms of F1-score, among all the approaches examined, regardless of the base model used. Consequently, Approach 1 demonstrated its superiority for modifying pre-trained image classification deep CNN models for classifying chest X-ray images between Normal, COVID-19, and Viral pneumonia. Regarding the optimal base CNN model, results are not conclusive for selecting a single model but show two out of the eleven examined candidates as suitable. The EfficientNetB4 and Xception -based models provided similar results for Approach 1 in terms of accuracy (98.04% vs 98.00% respectively), F1-score (98.22% vs 98.20%), Precision (98.52% vs 98.58%) and Recall (97.95% vs 97.87%), with the EfficientNetB4-based model being marginally better in most cases, while also achieving a marginally higher Jaccard index (96.52% vs 95.98%) and Dice coefficient (98.23% vs 97.95%). As a result, both models can be considered as suitable for the examined task.

TABLE 5.3: Classification performance (%) of the examined deep neural network architectures following Approach 2 when using the pre-trained weights for the base network and when training each network end-to-end.

Base model	End-to-end training						Pre-trained base					
	Accuracy	F1-score	Precision	Recall	Jaccard	Dice	Accuracy	F1-score	Precision	Recall	Jaccard	Dice
EfficientNetB4	96.45	96.60	97.38	95.86	92.45	96.08	93.22	92.12	95.46	89.61	86.13	92.55
EfficientNetB7	95.39	95.61	96.29	94.98	89.83	94.64	90.12	89.22	94.21	85.52	80.34	89.10
VGG16	94.66	94.83	95.61	94.15	88.70	94.01	93.94	93.74	94.40	93.13	86.28	92.64
Xception	96.72	97.26	97.80	96.80	93.31	96.54	93.49	93.90	94.62	93.29	86.39	92.70
InceptionResNetV2	96.70	96.12	95.83	96.58	91.68	95.66	93.94	94.02	95.63	92.57	86.23	92.60
InceptionV3	97.07	97.27	98.14	96.49	94.59	97.22	96.18	95.76	96.73	95.07	87.96	93.60
MobileNetV2	95.31	95.68	97.16	94.36	90.10	94.79	94.80	95.24	96.02	94.60	88.83	94.08
ResNet50V2	96.08	96.21	97.02	95.52	91.82	95.74	94.25	94.35	94.65	94.20	87.74	93.47
DenseNet121	96.18	96.55	96.88	96.25	92.89	96.31	95.42	96.06	96.80	95.44	90.64	95.09
DenseNet169	97.11	96.96	97.29	96.67	93.80	96.80	95.77	96.12	96.66	95.64	91.17	95.38
DenseNet201	96.52	96.73	97.05	96.51	92.64	96.18	95.04	95.02	95.86	94.26	89.15	94.26

Note: Results in bold denote the best performance for each metric and approach. Underlined results denote the overall best performance for each metric.

TABLE 5.4: Confusion matrix for the EfficientNetB4-based Approach 1 (end-to-end) without additional training or fine-tuning on the unseen COVID-19 data set

		Predicted		
		COVID-19	Normal	Viral pneumonia
Actual	COVID-19	234 (96.30%)	7 (2.88%)	2 (0.82%)
	Normal	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
	Viral pneumonia	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)

TABLE 5.5: Execution time and size of best performing models.

Base model	Approach	Trainable parameters	Epochs	Training time (s/epoch)
VGG16	Baseline	186,667,011	28	108s
EfficientNetB4	Approach 1 (End-to-end)	17,786,571	32	112s
Xception	Approach 1 (End-to-end)	21,077,675	20	111s
ResNet50V2	Approach 1 (Pre-trained base)	270,723	13	119s
InceptionV3	Approach 2 (End-to-end)	28,076,195	18	123s
Xception	Approach 2 (End-to-end)	27,114,795	21	118s
DenseNet169	Approach 2 (Pre-trained base)	5,520,643	18	166s

Note: Average execution times measured using TensorFlow and the Keras API on the Google Colab Pro platform (Nvidia Tesla T4 and P100 GPU, 24 GB RAM). All base models were initialised with weights pre-trained on the ImageNet data set.

TABLE 5.6: Classification performance (%) of the best configurations versus other works using the same data set for the same task.

Method	Accuracy	F1-score	Precision	Recall
Aslan et al. [15] CNN	98.14	98.20	98.16	98.26
Aslan et al. [15] CNN+BiLSTM	98.70	98.76	98.77	98.76
Chowdhury et al. [55] (NIA)	97.74	96.61	96.61	96.61
Chowdhury et al. [55] (IA)	97.94	97.94	97.95	97.94
Maiti et al. [168] (GHE+TBH)	96.00	96.67	97.00	95.67
Öksüz et al. [188]	98.30	97.61	97.43	97.78
Progga et al. [201]	n/a	98.00	98.00	98.00
Sakib et al. [229]	96.00	97.67	98.00	97.67
This work - Approach 1	98.04	98.22	98.52	97.95
This work - Approach 2	97.07	97.27	98.14	96.49

NIA: No Image Augmentation, IA: Image Augmentation, GHE: Global Histogram Equalisation, TBH: Top Bottom Hat Transform

Figure 5.4 depicts the aggregated confusion matrices, i.e. the sum of the confusion matrices from each fold of the 5-fold cross validation procedure, for Approach 1 (end-to-end training). It must be noted that since the additional images created through data augmentation (Section 5.1.2) were only used for training, the testing sets contained only the original images, thus the number of samples for each class in the confusion matrices is equal to the number of samples per class in the data set (Section 5.1.1). From these confusion matrices, it is evident that the two best performing models achieved almost similar performance in correctly classifying COVID-19 samples, with the EfficientNetB4-based model correctly classifying 215/219 COVID-19 samples and the Xception-based model 214/219. Despite other models also achieving similar performance for the COVID-19 samples, the EfficientNetB4 and Xception -based models for Approach 1 achieved the best balance across all the three available classes.

The EfficientNetB4 model belongs to the EfficientNet family which consists of 8 models, ranging from B0 to B7, and has been shown to achieve both higher accuracy and better efficiency than previous ConvNets, with reduced parameter size. This group of models was developed by Google AI researchers and was scaled down by balancing the depth, width and resolution which has led to effective results and it is also smaller and faster than existing deep learning models [259]. More specifically, the EfficientNetB4 achieved state-of-the-art 83.0% top-1 / 96.3% top-5 accuracy on ImageNet and has a size of 75 MB with over 19 million parameters [259]. The Xception model has previously achieved 79.0% top-1 / 94.5% top-5 accuracy on ImageNet and has a size of 88 MB with over 22 million parameters [52].

Interestingly, when using the pre-trained weights for the base networks, Approach 2 outperformed Approach 1 (maximum F1-score of 96.12% for DenseNet169 vs. 90.81% for ResNet50V2 respectively). Despite performing worse than Approach 1 with end-to-end training, it seems that the more complex architecture of Approach 2 led to a better use of the pre-trained features compared to the simpler architecture of Approach 1, when no end-to-end training was applied.

To further demonstrate the performance of the proposed approach, this research compared the results of the best model for each approach (EfficientNetB4-based Approach 1 and InceptionV3-based Approach 2, both with end-to-end training) to other works in the literature that used the same data set for the same classification task (COVID-19 vs. Normal vs. Viral Pneumonia), as shown in Table 5.6. Given the large number of chest X-ray data sets in the literature and the fact that many works combine multiple data sets to increase the number of available samples, this research opted to include in our comparison only works that used the exact same data set as this work, in order to provide a fair comparison. From Table 5.6, it is evident that the proposed approach achieves a higher F1-score (98.22%) compared to the other methods, except for the CNN+BiLSTM approach of Aslan et al. [15], which achieved a marginally higher F1-score (98.76%) by utilising the more computationally complex BiLSTM layers on top of the CNN layers.

In addition, this research used the Gradient-weighted Class Activation Mapping (Grad-CAM) method to visualise class activation heat maps for the best performing model (EfficientNetB4-base Approach 1), as shown in Figure 5.5 for four COVID-19-positive images. The Grad-CAM method uses the gradients of any target class in a classification network flowing into the final convolutional layer to produce a coarse localisation map that highlights the most important image regions for predicting the specific class. It is based on the CAM method that finds the discriminative regions for a CNN prediction through the computation of class activation maps, which assign importance to every position (i, j) in the last convolutional layer by computing the linear combination of the activations, weighted by the corresponding output weights for the observed class. Grad-CAM extends the CAM method by incorporating gradient information in the computation of the class activation maps (heat maps). By using the heat maps from the Grad-CAM method, we can examine the regions within the input image that the CNN model focuses for making the decision for each class. By examining the examples in Figure 5.5 for our best performing model, it is evident that the trained CNN model focuses on the areas of the lungs, as expected, and thus we can be confident that the model relies on features extracted from the image regions that contain the information regarding COVID-19, viral pneumonia, or healthy lungs, and not on information related to the images, to artefacts in the images, or to the source of the images.

FIGURE 5.3: Precision vs. Recall for the Baseline approach and Approaches 1 and 2 for end-to-end training.

Regarding the applicability of our work in clinical practice, research has shown that the severity of COVID-19-related findings on chest X-rays peaks after 10–12 days since initial symptoms onset, whereas they are not visible or are slightly visible during the first 3 days [288]. Consequently, the proposed models could assist with COVID-19 diagnosis after symptom onset. However, it must be noted that the American College of Radiology (ACR) [10] and the WHO [6] urge caution in using chest radiography as a primary diagnostic tool for COVID-19, with the WHO suggesting its use in cases that RT-PCR is not available at all or in a timely manner. In addition, despite the high classification performance of the proposed models on images from various sources, a larger study that would include numerous COVID-19-positive chest X-rays, acquired from multiple radiography devices at multiple stages of the disease, would be required for evaluating their suitability for real-world clinical practice. Nevertheless, the acquired results are very promising, demonstrating how deep learning image classification models could potentially provide crucial help on the diagnosis of COVID-19.

5.3 Summary

The global COVID-19 pandemic that started in 2019 demonstrated the need for quick, cheap, accessible and reliable diagnostic methods for detecting infected individuals. This research evaluated the performance of eleven deep convolutional neural network architectures for the task of classifying chest X-ray images as belonging to healthy individuals, individuals with COVID-19, or individuals with viral pneumonia. The eleven examined CNN models were selected due to their proven efficiency in image classification tasks and were modified in order to be adjusted for the task at hand. Supervised classification experiments using a 5-fold cross validation procedure were performed in order to evaluate the performance of three different modifications of the examined base CNN models on a data set with real chest X-ray images that contained normal images, COVID-19-positive images and viral pneumonia images. The EfficientNetB4 and the Xception-based models, using Approach 1 and end-to-end training, provided the best classification performance, reaching an accuracy of 98.04% and 98.00% respectively and an average F1-score of 98.22% and 98.20% respectively. Given the cost and accessibility of chest X-rays, the achieved results demonstrate the potential of the proposed approach for a relatively cheap and accessible diagnostic method for detecting COVID-19-positive individuals. Furthermore, the use of a data set with images sourced from various sources, indicates that the reported results are not constrained to a specific imaging device but can be generalised, as also demonstrated by the very high accuracy (96.30%)

		EfficientNetB4					EfficientNetB7					VGG16		
		COVID-19	Normal	Vir. Pneu.			COVID-19	Normal	Vir. Pneu.			COVID-19	Normal	Vir. Pneu.
Actual	COVID-19	215	3	1	Actual	COVID-19	211	4	4	Actual	COVID-19	208	4	7
	Normal	1	1323	17		Normal	5	1313	23		Normal	13	1284	44
	Vir. Pneu.	1	33	1311		Vir. Pneu.	8	44	1293		Vir. Pneu.	11	73	1261

		Xception					InceptionResNetV2					InceptionV3		
		COVID-19	Normal	Vir. Pneu.			COVID-19	Normal	Vir. Pneu.			COVID-19	Normal	Vir. Pneu.
Actual	COVID-19	214	2	3	Actual	COVID-19	210	4	5	Actual	COVID-19	199	3	17
	Normal	2	1329	10		Normal	4	1321	16		Normal	11	1288	42
	Vir. Pneu.	3	37	1305		Vir. Pneu.	5	41	1299		Vir. Pneu.	3	35	1307

		Mobile-NetV2					Res-Net50V2					Dense-Net121		
		COVID-19	Normal	Vir. Pneu.			COVID-19	Normal	Vir. Pneu.			COVID-19	Normal	Vir. Pneu.
Actual	COVID-19	212	4	3	Actual	COVID-19	215	3	1	Actual	COVID-19	214	3	2
	Normal	7	1315	19		Normal	3	1320	18		Normal	4	1324	13
	Vir. Pneu.	9	45	1291		Vir. Pneu.	5	44	1296		Vir. Pneu.	9	52	1284

		Dense-Net169					Dense-Net201		
		COVID-19	Normal	Vir. Pneu.			COVID-19	Normal	Vir. Pneu.
Actual	COVID-19	216	3	0	Actual	COVID-19	210	6	3
	Normal	7	1320	14		Normal	1	1324	16
	Vir. Pneu.	4	44	1297		Vir. Pneu.	8	46	1291

FIGURE 5.4: Aggregated confusion matrices for Approach 1 (end-to-end training).

FIGURE 5.5: Grad-CAM visualisation for the COVID-19 class using the EfficientNetB4-based Approach 1 model for four chest X-ray images.

achieved when classifying the images of an unseen data set. Nevertheless, a larger study, including numerous COVID-19-positive chest X-rays, acquired from multiple radiography devices, would be required for evaluating the suitability of the proposed approach in real clinical practice. The next chapter, includes a replication study using a much larger data set of chest X-ray images. In addition exploring the use of the latest advances in deep learning, such as vision transformers.

Chapter 6

IEViT: An Input Enhanced Vision Transformer Architecture for Chest X-ray Image Classification

This research continued by using a larger data set of chest X-ray images with added pathologies and thoroughly examining the generalisation capability of the developed models by training and testing the models on various data sets from various sources and with X-ray images obtained by various X-ray machines. Along with utilising the most recent developments in deep learning-based image classification, vision transformers.

In recent years, the use of deep learning methods and convolutional neural networks (CNNs) has proven to be very effective in various computer vision-oriented tasks, including image classification, image segmentation, and object detection [150]. Based on this success, AI/machine learning systems have been extensively researched to automate image analysis in the clinical field, such as for tuberculosis diagnosis [164], and the detection of pneumonia [136], COVID-19 [187, 197], pneumothorax [113], pneumoconiosis [279], lung cancer [123], as well as for other radiology analysis tasks [298].

The success of CNNs in generic image classification tasks led to their widespread adoption for the classification of various types of specialised images with or without transfer learning, as explained above. Nevertheless, other architectures [72] have recently gained attention due to their enhanced performance compared to CNNs. Inspired by the success of Transformers in Natural Language Processing (NLP), researchers have recently tried to apply Transformers directly to images [96], using several approaches. Some works combined CNN architectures with self-attention. Ramachandran et al. [212] suggested substituting all convolutional layers for self-attention layers instead of using self-attention layers on top of them, whereas Bello et al. [27] proposed to improve CNNs by substituting some convolutional layers for self-attention layers. However, these approaches exhibited high computational cost due to the large size of the images that led to an enormous growth in the complexity of self-attention. Wu et al. [291] used convolutional layers to extract feature maps of the input images that were then fed to stacked Transformer layers for computing the final output.

The Vision Transformer (ViT) [72] architecture is the first attempt for a pure Transformer architecture that achieved state-of-the-art results on image classification. ViT adapts the BERT [70] Transformer-based architecture for understanding language to image classification via some modifications. To this end, images are first divided into rectangular patches, which are then treated as tokens for which embeddings are computed. After the addition of positional embeddings to encode the structure of the image, the patch embeddings are fed to a series of Transformer layers for the creation of the final feature map. Experimental results showed that the various ViT variants are able to achieve better performance in ImageNet, CIFAR, and VTAB classification compared to common CNNs [72].

Following the success of the ViT model, various variants have been proposed. Touvron et al. [264] introduced the data-efficient image transformers (DeiT), which performed better than the original ViT architecture on ImageNet, achieving an accuracy of 85.2%. Yuan et al. [299] proposed a layer-wise Tokens-To-Token Vision Transformer (T2T-ViT), to encode the significant structure for every token, contrary to the simple tokenisation utilised in ViT [72].

They tested their method on ImageNet and achieved an 82.3% Top-1 accuracy, outperforming the original ViT architecture. Chen et al. [50] proposed an original double-branch vision transformer that also employed a cross-attention-based token fusion scheme, achieving a 82.8% Top-1 accuracy on ImageNet. Li et al. [149] introduced locality to vision transformers by incorporating 2D depth-wise convolutions. This basic concept was inspired from comparisons between inverted residual blocks and feed-forward networks, and achieved a 94.2% Top-5 accuracy on ImageNet, the best among the other evaluated architectures. Wang et al. [277] proposed the Pyramid Vision Transformer (PVT), which incorporates the pyramid structure from CNNs to the vision transformer architecture, achieving a 18.3% Top-1 error on ImageNet. Liu et al. [160] proposed a hierarchical vision Transformer architecture that utilises shifted windows and has reduced computational complexity with respect to image size compared to the original ViT model.

Motivated from the importance of automating the diagnosis of chest X-ray images, from the success of self-attention in transformer models, and from the increasing interest in models utilising attention mechanisms within convnets [302], this research introduced the *Input Enhanced Vision Transformer (IEViT)*, an enhanced Vision Transformer architecture for classifying chest X-ray images. The proposed model builds on the ViT architecture and introduces a CNN block that is used to create an embedding of the full input image, which is then iteratively fed to each Transformer encoder layer by concatenating the image embedding to the output of each Transformer encoder layer. The proposed model, as well as the original ViT model, were then evaluated on four chest X-ray image data sets. Classification experiments demonstrated that IEViT outperformed ViT for all the variants and data sets examined, achieving a maximum F1-score of 98.48% for Normal vs. Children Pneumonia, 100% for Normal vs. Tuberculosis, 98.05% for Normal vs. Viral Pneumonia vs. COVID-19, and 96.39% for Normal vs. COVID-19.

The contribution of this work can be summarised as follows: (i) This research evaluated the performance of the ViT “Base” and “Large” variants on four chest X-ray image data sets for the task of classifying various pathological conditions reflected on the images. (ii) This research proposed IEViT, a novel enhanced vision transformer architecture that improves the performance of both the “Base” and “Large” ViT variants on all the examined chest X-ray image data sets. (iii) This research provided a detailed performance evaluation of the proposed enhanced Vision Transformer architecture on the examined chest X-ray image data sets.

6.1 Research Methodology

This research proposed an Input Enhanced ViT (IEViT), an enhanced vision transformer architecture for the classification of chest X-ray images. The proposed architecture was evaluated against the original ViT architecture on four chest X-ray image data sets that contained images associated with children pneumonia, tuberculosis, COVID-19, viral pneumonia, as well as with no pathology (healthy individuals). This research opted to evaluate our proposed method on images originating from various sources, acquired using different radiography devices, and associated with various pathological conditions, in order to validate its robustness and generalisation in comparison to the original ViT architecture.

6.1.1 Data set

The four data sets used in this work are the following: (i) The *Kermany et al.* data set [133], which consists of normal chest X-ray scans and scans associated with pneumonia of children patients (1-5 years old), acquired from [134]. (ii) The *Tuberculosis Chest X-ray Database* [208], which contains normal chest X-ray images and chest X-ray images associated with Tuberculosis, collected from three publicly accessible databases [1, 26, 205]. (iii) The *COVID-19 radiography database* [56, 207], which consists of normal chest X-ray images, chest X-ray images associated with viral pneumonia, and chest X-ray images associated with COVID-19, acquired from multiple sources [97, 116, 119, 133, 205, 287]. (iv) The *COVIDx* data set [274],

which contains normal and COVID-19-positive chest X-ray images, sourced from five different publicly available data repositories [58, 59, 65, 204, 205]. To the best of our knowledge, COVIDx has the most COVID-19 positive images out of all the publicly available data sets.

Sample X-ray images from the examined data sets are provided in Figure 6.1, whereas the number of images per class in each data set is presented in Table 6.1.

FIGURE 6.1: Sample X-ray images from the examined data sets: (a, b) Kermamy, (c) Tuberculosis, (d, e) COVID-19 radiography, (f) COVIDx. .

TABLE 6.1: Data set details

Data set	Number of images per class			
	Normal	Pneumonia	Tuberculosis	COVID-19
Kermamy	1349/234	3883/624	-	-
Tuberculosis	3500	-	700	-
COVID-19	10202	1345	-	3615
COVIDx	13992/200	-	-	16490/200

Note: */* refers to the official train/test split. 80%/20% split used otherwise.

6.1.2 The original Vision Transformer (ViT) architecture

Proposed by Dosovitskiy et al. [72], the Vision Transformer (ViT) architecture is a pure transformer approach that can perform on par or even outperform common CNN architectures for image classification when trained on large amounts of image data. The input image to the ViT architecture is split into square patches, with each patch flattened and concatenated across the image's channels in order to create a vector representation of each image patch. An embedding of each vector is then created via linear projection to a specific dimension. A learnable position embedding is also added to each patch in order to allow the ViT model to learn about the structure of the input images. The patch embeddings are then fed to stacked Transformer layers and the output is passed to an MLP head for the final classification. Details about the various ViT variants are provided in Table 6.2.

FIGURE 6.2: Overview of the proposed IEViT model.

6.1.3 The proposed Input Enhanced Vision Transformer (IEViT)

The proposed IEViT approach is partially motivated by the ResNet [100] architecture, which introduced the skip connection, i.e. the addition of the original input to the output of each convolutional block, which brought about the concept of a residual network. Our approach builds on this concept for modifying the ViT [72] architecture. To this end, a representation of the original input image is iteratively added to the output of each Transformer encoder layer. This is achieved by first designing a convolutional block in parallel with the ViT network. The CNN block takes as an input the whole input image and outputs an embedding of the whole image, which is then iteratively concatenated to the output of each Transformer encoder layer, thereby making the network to always “remember” the full image at the end of each transformer block output. An overview of the proposed IEViT architecture is provided in Figure 6.2.

The proposed CNN block consists of stacked 2D convolutional layers, followed by a 1D global maximum pooling layer, as shown in Figure 6.2. Three 2D convolutional layers were used in our experiments, with the first using 16 filters with a kernel size of 3, the second using 256 filters with a kernel size of 5, and the third using D filters with a kernel size of 5. The input to the CNN block is an image of size $H \times W \times C$, where H is the height of the image, W the width, and C the number of channels. Then, the max pooling layer is used in order to compute the output vector x_{img} of size D , which is a mapping of the input image to D dimensions.

For the vision transformer part of the architecture, similar to ViT [72], the input image is divided into $N = \frac{H \cdot W}{P^2}$ patches, where (P, P) is the resolution of each patch, which are then flattened across all dimensions to create a sequence of flattened patches x_p of total size $N \times (P^2 \cdot C)$. Then, the patch embeddings are created by mapping the patches to D dimensions using a trainable linear projection, as follows:

$$\mathbf{z}_p = [x_p^1 E, x_p^2 E, \dots, x_p^N E], \quad E \in \mathbb{R}^{(P^2 \cdot C) \times D} \quad (6.1)$$

Then, as in ViT [72], a learnable embedding x_{class} of size D , similar to BERT’s [class] token [70], is prepended to the sequence of patch embeddings, while position embeddings

TABLE 6.2: Details of the ViT and IEViT model variants

Model	Patch size ($P \times P$)	Layers (L)	Hidden size (D)	MLP size	Heads	Params
ViT-B/16	16×16	12	768	3072	12	85.8M
ViT-B/32	32×32	12	768	3072	12	87.4M
ViT-L/16	16×16	24	1024	4096	16	303.3M
ViT-L/32	32×32	24	1024	4096	16	305.5M
IEViT-B/16	16×16	12	768	3072	12	90.8M
IEViT-B/32	32×32	12	768	3072	12	92.4M
IEViT-L/16	16×16	24	1024	4096	16	309.9M
IEViT-L/32	32×32	24	1024	4096	16	312.1M

are added to the sequence of patch embeddings in order to incorporate information about the position of each patch in the original image. A standard learnable 1D position embedding of size D is used for each of the $N + 1$ embeddings in the patch embedding matrix, with the position for the additional x_{class} embedding set as 0. The initial patch embeddings \mathbf{z}_0 are computed as follows:

$$\mathbf{z}_0 = [x_{class}, \mathbf{z}_p] + E_{pos}, \quad E_{pos} \in \mathbb{R}^{(N+1) \times D} \quad (6.2)$$

Then, L transformer encoder layers [72, 270] are stacked, with \mathbf{z}_0 being the input of the first layer. $\hat{\mathbf{z}}_l$ is then computed by concatenating the image embedding x_{img} to the output \mathbf{z}_l of each Transformer encoder layer l , $l = 1, 2, \dots, L$, as follows:

$$\hat{\mathbf{z}}_l = [\mathbf{z}_l, x_{img}], \quad \hat{\mathbf{z}}_l \in \mathbb{R}^{(N+1+l) \times D} \quad (6.3)$$

$\hat{\mathbf{z}}_l$ is then fed to the next Transformer encoder layer, or to the next layer of the architecture if $l = L$. As a result, contrary to ViT, each Transformer encoder layer in IEViT is fed a representation of the whole input image in addition to the output of the previous Transformer encoder layer, as also shown in Figure 6.2.

As shown in Table 6.2, the original ViT architecture supported different configurations that were adopted from BERT [70]. Following the same approach, the proposed IEViT architecture adopts the “Base” and “Large” models using a similar notation to ViT. To this end, IEViT-B/16 refers to the “Base” variant with an image patch size of 16×16 , whereas similarly, IEViT-L/32 refers to the “Large” variant with an image patch size of 32×32 . Details about the proposed model’s variants, as well as the variants of the original ViT are provided in Table 6.2.

It must also be noted that Keras and the *vit-keras*¹ implementation of ViT were used for all our experiments and as the backbone for the implementation of IEViT.

6.1.4 Training and Classification

To evaluate the proposed IEViT architecture against the original ViT architecture for the four examined chest X-ray data sets, this research compared each of the B/16, B/32, L/16, L/32 variants of the proposed architecture against the same variants of the original ViT architecture. Transfer learning was used for both architectures, with the ViT models and the ViT parts of the proposed models being initialised with weights pre-trained on the ImageNet [221] data set. For the proposed architecture, the additional parts were initialised randomly and their weights were trained during the fine-tuning process. For each data set, the classifier on top of each model was set according to the number of classes in the data set, and end-to-end training was used for the fine-tuning.

¹<https://github.com/faustomorales/vit-keras>

TABLE 6.3: Data augmentation procedure.

Augmentation step	Options/Range
Rotation at random angle	[-40 , 40] degrees
Random flipping	{horizontally, vertically}
Random shifting across the height	10% of the total height
Random shifting across the width	10% of the total width
Random shifting of brightness	[0.5 , 1.5]
Random shearing in counter-clockwise direction	[0 , 0.1] radians
Random zooming within a range	[0.9 , 1.1]
Rescaling by factor	1/255

Note: “nearest” image filling mode used where needed

Training was performed using Cross-Entropy as the loss function (Eq. 6.4), the Adam optimiser, a batch size of 16 and a 0.0001 learning rate. The low learning rate was selected in order to better adapt the pre-trained weights to the new data.

$$L_{CE} = - \sum_{c=1}^M y_{o,c} \log(p_{o,c}) \quad (6.4)$$

with M being the number of classes ($M_{\text{Keremany}} = 2$, $M_{\text{Tuberculosis}} = 2$, $M_{\text{COVID-19}} = 3$, $M_{\text{COVIDx}} = 2$), $y_{o,c}$ having a value of 1 if observation o belongs to class c and a value of 0 if not, and $p_{o,c}$ being the predicted probability that observation o belongs to class c .

Label smoothing was also used for the training process in order to reduce over-fitting and encourage the model to be less confident, thus leading to better generalisation. Label smoothing is a regularisation technique, proposed by Szegedy et al. [257] for improving the performance of the Inception architecture on the ImageNet data set, which has since been adopted by many state-of-the-art deep learning classification approaches [215, 310]. When using cross-entropy as the loss function, training aims to minimise L_{CE} , with $y_{o,c}$ being a “hard” target $\in \{0,1\}$. When using label smoothing, a “soft” target $y_{o,c}^{LS}$ is used instead, computed as:

$$y_{o,c}^{LS} = y_{o,c}(1 - \alpha) + \frac{\alpha}{M} \quad (6.5)$$

where M is the number of classes and α the label smoothing parameter, which was set to $\alpha = 0.1$ in this work.

In addition to label smoothing, data augmentation was used during training, as it has been proven to be an effective tool for image classification [199], and is mostly used in deep learning approaches to increase the amount of training data and assist in avoiding over-fitting [289]. To this end, more training images were created using the original training images by following the augmentation steps described in Table 6.3.

A uniform probability distribution was used to create the random values for the data augmentation procedure, and batches of augmented images were created in real-time during each training procedure using the *Keras ImageDataGenerator* class. It must also be pointed out that data augmentation was used only for training. Consequently, the reported results on the test data refer to original images only.

6.2 Results

6.2.1 Classification experiments

The proposed IEViT models, as well as the original ViT models, for the B/16, B/32, L/16, and L/32 variants were evaluated via supervised classification experiments on the four examined chest X-ray data sets for the respective 2-class and 3-class problems, i.e. Normal

TABLE 6.4: Classification performance (%) on the Kermany et al. children pneumonia data set.

Model	Accuracy	Recall	Precision	F1-score
IEViT-B/16	97.76	98.46	97.96	98.21
IEViT-B/32	97.12	98.98	96.50	97.72
IEViT-L/16	97.60	99.23	96.99	98.10
IEViT-L/32	98.08	99.74	97.25	98.48
ViT-B/16	92.63	97.18	91.55	94.28
ViT-B/32	90.71	98.21	88.25	92.96
ViT-L/16	91.99	98.97	89.35	93.92
ViT-L/32	90.22	98.72	87.30	92.66
CNN-block-B	69.55	91.28	69.53	78.94
CNN-block-L	67.95	88.21	69.08	77.48

Note: Results in bold denote the highest value per metric.

vs. Pneumonia for the Kermany data set, Normal vs. Tuberculosis for the Tuberculosis data set, Normal vs. COVID-19 vs. Viral Pneumonia for the COVID-19 data set, and Normal vs. COVID-19 for the COVIDx data set. The training set of each data set was further split into a training (90%) and validation (10%) set, whereas final performance results were reported on the unseen test sets in order to provide a fair estimate of classification performance and reduce over-fitting.

For all models, classification performance was measured using the following metrics: Accuracy, Recall (Sensitivity), Precision, and F1-score, which is the harmonic mean of Precision and Recall, defined as:

$$\text{F1-score} = 2 \cdot \frac{\text{Precision} \cdot \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \quad (6.6)$$

In the case of F1-score, recall, and precision, the metrics were computed for all classes and the average across classes (macro average) was reported as the final value of the metric. It must also be noted that due to the class imbalance of some data sets, F1-score was used as the primary performance benchmark, as classification accuracy can be biased in cases of unbalanced data sets. Tensorflow and the Keras API were employed for the proposed experimental evaluation. It must also be noted that input images were all rescaled to 224×224 . The classification performance achieved by the examined IEViT and ViT variants on the Kermany, Tuberculosis, COVID-19 and COVIDx data sets is reported in Table 6.4, 6.5, 6.6, and 6.7 respectively, in terms of the examined metrics, whereas confusion matrices for the IEViT variants are provided in Figure 6.3.

6.2.2 Classification results per data set

Classification results for the proposed model’s variants, as well as for the original ViT model variants, on the Kermany et al. children pneumonia data set are presented in Table 6.4. From this table, as well as from Table 6.8 that shows the per variant performance difference in terms of F1-score, it is evident that all the proposed IEViT model’s variants outperformed their respective ViT model variants for all the examined metrics. The achieved improvement in terms of F1-score spans from +3.93% for the B/16 variant to +5.82% for the L/32 variant, with an average improvement of +4.67% across all variants. Results demonstrated stability across the examined models, with an average F1-score within the range of 92.66%-94.28% for the original ViT variants, compared to 97.72%-98.48% for the proposed IEViT model’s

TABLE 6.5: Classification performance (%) on the Tuberculosis data set.

Model	Accuracy	Recall	Precision	F1-score
IEViT-B/16	99.76	100.0	98.59	99.29
IEViT-B/32	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
IEViT-L/16	99.76	100.0	98.59	99.29
IEViT-L/32	99.29	97.14	98.55	97.84
ViT-B/16	99.64	100.0	97.90	98.94
ViT-B/32	99.41	96.43	100.0	98.94
ViT-L/16	98.81	98.57	94.52	96.50
ViT-L/32	98.69	92.14	100.0	95.91
CNN-block-B	89.43	68.21	94.37	73.72
CNN-block-L	88.48	65.36	93.93	70.27

Note: Results in bold denote the highest value per metric.

TABLE 6.6: Classification performance (%) on the COVID-19 radiography data set.

Model	Accuracy	Recall	Precision	F1-score
IEViT-B/16	97.93	95.54	98.29	96.82
IEViT-B/32	97.37	95.28	98.34	96.74
IEViT-L/16	96.18	91.17	97.26	93.90
IEViT-L/32	98.59	97.09	99.06	98.05
ViT-B/16	97.96	94.17	98.77	96.27
ViT-B/32	97.01	94.36	98.17	96.16
ViT-L/16	96.54	90.02	97.10	92.95
ViT-L/32	96.08	91.40	97.64	94.21
CNN-block-B	81.54	70.24	74.38	71.99
CNN-block-L	83.68	72.00	77.41	74.24

Note: Results in bold denote the highest value per metric.

TABLE 6.7: Classification performance (%) on the COVIDx data set.

Model	Accuracy	Recall	Precision	F1-score
IEViT-B/16	96.50	93.50	99.47	96.39
IEViT-B/32	95.00	91.00	98.91	94.79
IEViT-L/16	95.25	91.00	99.45	95.04
IEViT-L/32	95.00	90.50	99.45	94.76
ViT-B/16	95.00	90.50	99.45	94.76
ViT-B/32	92.00	85.00	98.84	91.40
ViT-L/16	93.25	87.00	99.43	92.80
ViT-L/32	92.75	88.00	97.24	92.39
CNN-block-B	90.50	90.50	90.50	90.50
CNN-block-L	91.00	91.00	91.00	91.00

Note: Results in bold denote the highest value per metric.

TABLE 6.8: F1-scores (%) and their difference (Δ) for IEViT and ViT for all examined data sets.

Data set	ViT-B/16	IEViT-B/16	Δ	ViT-L/16	IEViT-L/16	Δ	ViT-B/32	IEViT-B/32	Δ	ViT-L/32	IEViT-L/32	Δ	Avg Δ
Kermany	94.28	98.21	3.93	93.92	98.10	4.18	92.96	97.72	4.76	92.66	98.48	5.82	4.67
Tuberculosis	98.94	99.29	0.35	96.50	99.29	2.79	98.18	100.0	1.82	95.91	97.84	1.93	1.72
COVID-19	96.27	96.85	0.58	92.95	93.90	0.95	96.16	96.74	0.59	94.21	98.05	3.84	1.49
COVIDx	94.76	96.39	1.63	92.80	95.04	2.24	91.40	94.79	3.39	92.39	94.76	2.38	2.41
Average	96.06	97.69	1.62	94.04	96.58	2.54	94.67	97.31	2.64	93.79	97.28	3.49	2.57

Figure 6.3 displays 16 confusion matrices for IEViT variants across four datasets. The matrices are organized in a 4x4 grid. The rows correspond to the datasets: Kermany et al., Tuberculosis, COVID-19 rad., and COVIDx. The columns correspond to the IEViT variants: B/16, B/32, L/16, and L/32. Each matrix shows the relationship between Actual and Predicted values for the classes in the dataset.

FIGURE 6.3: Confusion matrices for all the IEViT variants for the four examined datasets. Results refer to the test set of each dataset.

variants. The best performance for the Kermany et al. children pneumonia data set was achieved by the IEViT-L/32 model, reaching an F1-score of 98.48%, an accuracy of 98.08%, a recall of 99.74%, and a precision of 97.25%, as shown in Table 6.4.

Results for the proposed model's variants, as well as for the original ViT model variants, on the Tuberculosis data set are presented in Table 6.5. From this table and from Table 6.8, it is evident that all the proposed IEViT model's variants outperformed their respective ViT model variants for all the examined metrics. The achieved improvement in terms of F1-score spans from +0.35% for the B/16 variant to +2.79% for the L/16 variant, with an average improvement of +1.72% across all variants. F1-scores for the ViT model variants ranged from 95.91%-98.94%, compared to 97.84%-100% for the proposed IEViT model's variants. The best performance for the Tuberculosis data set was achieved using the IEViT-B/32 model, reaching an F1-score, accuracy, recall, and precision of 100%, as shown in Table 6.5.

For the COVID-19 radiography data set, results for the proposed model's variants, as well as for the original ViT model variants, are presented in Table 6.6. As shown in this table, as well as in Table 6.8, all the proposed IEViT model's variants outperformed their respective ViT model variants for all the examined metrics. The improvement achieved in terms of F1-score ranged between +0.58% for the B/16 variant to +3.84% for the L/32 variant, with an average improvement of +1.49% across all variants. F1-scores for the ViT model variants ranged from 92.95%-96.27%, compared to 93.90%-98.05% for the proposed IEViT model's variants. The best performance for the COVID-19 radiography data set was achieved using the IEViT-L/32 model, reaching an F1-score of 98.05%, an accuracy of 98.59%, a recall of 97.09%, and a precision of 99.06%, as shown in Table 6.6.

Results for the COVIDx data set for the original ViT variants, as well as the proposed IEViT variants are reported in Table 6.7. From this table and from Table 6.8, it is evident that all the proposed IEViT model's variants outperformed their respective ViT model variants for all the examined metrics. The achieved improvement in terms of F1-score ranged from +1.63% for the B/16 variant to +3.39% for the B/32 variant, with an average improvement of +2.41% across all variants. For the ViT model variants, F1-scores ranged from 91.40%-94.76%, compared to 94.76%-96.39% for the proposed IEViT model's variants. The best performance for the COVIDx data set was achieved using the IEViT-B/16 model, reaching an F1-score of 96.39%, an accuracy of 96.50%, a recall of 93.50%, and a precision of 99.47%, as shown in Table 6.7.

TABLE 6.9: F1-scores (%) for each data set using IEViT variants and the examined CNN models.

Model	Data set			
	Kermany	Tuberculosis	COVID-19	COVIDx
InceptionV3	94.76	99.28	97.86	97.19
Xception	95.24	96.68	96.92	97.70
ResNet50V2	95.13	98.55	97.70	98.48
EfficientNetB4	94.15	94.74	98.05	98.48
InceptionResNetV2	95.20	97.06	96.26	98.22
IEViT-B/16	98.21	99.29	96.85	96.39
IEViT-B/32	97.72	100.0	96.74	94.79
IEViT-L/16	98.10	99.29	93.90	95.04
IEViT-L/32	98.48	97.84	98.05	94.76

Note: Results in bold denote the best performance for each dataset.

6.2.3 Ablation study

The acquired experimental results demonstrate that the addition of the CNN block in the ViT architecture and the concatenation of its output to the output of each Transformer encoder layer led to a consistently improved classification performance of IEViT over ViT for all the examined data sets and variants. To further validate the contribution of the CNN block to the improvement in performance and to examine whether the combination of the CNN block and ViT is justified or the CNN block on its own is able to perform on par with IEViT, we evaluated the performance of the CNN block by creating a model consisting of only the CNN block and the MLP head. The “Base” ($D = 768$) and “Large” ($D = 1024$) variants of the CNN block were evaluated on the four examined data sets, using the same training parameters (including data augmentation) as for the ViT and the IEViT experiments.

Classification results for the CNN block variants are provided in Table 6.4, 6.5, 6.6, and 6.7 for each data set respectively. From these tables, it is evident that the CNN block variants on their own provide significantly worse performance than the respective IEViT and ViT variants. For the Kermany et al. children pneumonia data set, the CNN block achieved a maximum F1-score of 78.94%, compared to 98.48% for IEViT and 94.28% for ViT, whereas for the Tuberculosis data set, the CNN block achieved a maximum F1-score of 73.72%, compared to 100% for IEViT and 98.94% for ViT. For the COVID-19 radiography data set, the CNN block achieved a maximum F1-score of 74.24%, compared to 98.05% for IEViT and 96.27% for ViT, while for the COVIDx data set, the CNN block achieved a maximum F1-score of 91%, compared to 96.39% for IEViT and 94.76% for ViT. Consequently, the superiority of the IEViT variants over their respective ViT variants indicates that the introduction of the CNN block is significant for boosting the performance of the proposed IEViT model.

6.2.4 Comparison to established CNN models

To further assess the suitability of the proposed model, the performance of five well-established CNN models was evaluated on the four examined data sets. The CNN models used for the comparison with IEViT were InceptionV3 [257], Xception [52], ResNet50V2 [100], EfficientNetB4 [259], and InceptionResNetV2 [256]. All models were initialised with weights pre-trained on the ImageNet data set and were then fine-tuned on the examined data sets using end-to-end training and the same training parameters (including data augmentation) as for the ViT and the IEViT experiments. It must be noted that the default Keras implementations of the examined CNN models were used for the experimental evaluation.

The F1-scores achieved by the examined CNN models, as well as by the four IEViT variants, are provided for each data set in Table 6.9. The IEViT-L/32 variant achieved the best

TABLE 6.10: Best performing IEViT model per data set.

Data set	Model	Accuracy	Recall	Precision	F1-score
Kermany	IEViT-L/32	98.08	99.74	97.25	98.48
Tuberculosis	IEViT-B/32	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
COVID-19	IEViT-L/32	98.59	97.09	99.06	98.05
COVIDx	IEViT-B/16	96.50	93.50	99.47	96.39

performance for the Kermany et al. children pneumonia data set, with an F1-score of 98.48% compared to 95.24% achieved by the best performing CNN model (Xception). Regarding the Tuberculosis data set, the IEViT-B/32 variant performed the best, achieving an F1-score of 100% compared to 99.28% for the best performing InceptionV3 CNN model. For the COVID-19 radiography data set, the best performance was provided by both the IEViT-L/32 variant and the EfficientNetB4 CNN model, with both achieving an F1-score of 98.05%. Finally, the EfficientNetB4 model provided the best performance for the COVIDx data set, achieving an F1-score of 98.48% compared to 96.39% achieved by the best performing IEViT variant (IEViT-B/16).

6.3 Discussion

By examining the experimental results, it is evident that the proposed IEViT enhancement of the ViT architecture consistently results in improved performance for all the examined variants and data sets. As shown in Table 6.8, the average improvement across data sets over the original ViT model in terms of the F1-score was +1.62% for the B/16 variant, +2.64% for B/32, +2.54% for L/16, and +3.49% for L/32. For the B/16, B/32, and L/16 variants, the lowest improvement was achieved for the COVID-19 radiography data set, ranging from +0.58% to +0.95%, whereas the lowest improvement for the L/32 variant was achieved for the Tuberculosis data set (+1.93%).

It is also worth mentioning that different IEViT variants performed the best for each data set, as shown in Table 6.10. Variant L/32 provided the best performance for the Kermany and COVID-19 radiography data sets, B/32 for the Tuberculosis data set, and B/16 for the COVIDx data set. Consequently, the selection of the most suitable variant depends on the task at hand and would require experimentation and validation experiments on the related data. Furthermore, as shown in Table 6.9, well-established CNN models can achieve comparable (COVID-19 data set) or better (COVIDx data set) performance than IEViT in some cases, whereas IEViT performs better in other cases (Kermany and Tuberculosis data sets). Consequently, the task at hand and the computational complexity of the models used must be taken into consideration when selecting the most appropriate model. Nevertheless, as shown in Table 6.8, the IEViT-B/16 variant achieved the highest average F1-score (97.69%) across all data sets, indicating that it can be a good generic solution for X-ray image classification tasks. To this end, the B/16 variant can be selected when there are computational or other constraints that do not allow a thorough experimentation with all the available variants.

The proposed IEViT enhancement of the ViT architecture comes at a cost in terms of computational complexity. The addition of convolution layers, as well as the increase in size of the input to the Transformer encoder layers, results in an increase in the number of trainable parameters of the proposed models compared to the original ViT models. As shown in Table 6.2, the IEViT “Base” variants have approximately 5 million more trainable parameters compared to the respective ViT “Base” variants, whereas the IEViT “Large” variants have approximately 6.5 million more trainable parameters compared to the respective ViT “Large” variants. Nevertheless, as shown in Figure 6.4, this increase in complexity (number of parameters) led in all cases to improved performance, with some cases exhibiting a substantial improvement (up to +5.82% in F1-score for the L/32 variant and the Kermany data set), thus this increase in complexity can be justified.

FIGURE 6.4: F1-score (%) achieved for each data set and model variant vs. the number of parameters (millions) of the model. (a) “Base” variant, (b) “Large” variant.

To ensure the generalisation ability of the proposed models, various measures were taken to avoid overfitting. For each data set, the models were trained and tested on independent sets, where the final test set was completely “unseen” to the training process. Models were optimised for a validation set which was selected out of the training set. Furthermore, a stratified random sampling was used to create the train/validation/test splits when no official split was available, in order to ensure that the class distribution within the various sets was the same. The use of data augmentation during the training procedure further helped in addressing overfitting as it introduces variation in the training data and has been shown to improve the generalisation ability of deep learning models and reduce overfitting [243]. Similarly, the use of the employed label smoothing technique has also been shown to reduce overfitting and lead to better generalisation [257]. The proposed IEViT variants, as well as the original ViT variants were trained and evaluated on four diverse X-ray image data sets. Performance was consistent across data sets for both models, with IEViT consistently outperforming ViT for all the data sets. Finally, the F1-score was used as the benchmark metric for the performance of the examined models in order to ensure a fair performance evaluation, as the accuracy metric can be heavily biased towards the majority class in the data set and thus lead to erroneous conclusions.

The proposed IEViT model built upon the state-of-the-art original ViT model for image classification and achieved consistently better performance than ViT for the classification of chest X-ray images, using transfer learning via weights pre-trained on ImageNet. Given their widespread availability, the ability to use weights pre-trained for the original ViT model is also an advantageous characteristic of IEViT, as IEViT models can be easily trained using transfer learning for various image classification tasks, without the need to train the model on huge data sets. Furthermore, the use of various data sets that contained chest X-ray images acquired from various sources, using different radiography devices, indicates that IEViT is able to generalise well and is not limited to images acquired under specific settings and using specific radiography devices. Considering this and given the reported experimental results, it is evident that the proposed IEViT model constitutes a powerful solution for chest X-ray image classification that is able to consistently outperform the original ViT model variants on a set of diverse chest X-ray image data sets.

6.4 Summary

This research evaluated the performance of the state-of-the-art Vision Transformer (ViT) architecture for the task of classifying various pathological conditions in chest X-ray images, and proposed the novel IEViT architecture that outperformed the original ViT for all the variants and data sets examined. Experiments on a data set for children pneumonia, a data set for Tuberculosis, a data set for COVID-19 and viral pneumonia, as well as a data set for COVID-19, demonstrated the consistent improvement in classification performance of the proposed IEViT model's variants over the respective original ViT model's variants. Classification performance in terms of F1-score reached 98.4% for the children pneumonia data set using the IEViT-L/32 variant, 100% for the Tuberculosis data set using the IEViT-B/32 variant, 98.05% for the COVID-19 and viral pneumonia data set using the IEViT-L/32 variant, and 96.39% for the COVID-19 data set using the IEViT-B/16 variant.

Given the relatively low cost and the widespread accessibility of chest X-ray imaging, the use of the proposed IEViT model can potentially offer a powerful, but relatively cheap and accessible method for assisting diagnosis using chest X-ray images. Furthermore, the variety of data sets and image sources within the data sets indicates that the proposed solution is not constrained to images acquired using a specific device under specific settings, but can be generalised. Finally, the successful use of transfer learning, by using weights pre-trained on generic images, suggests that the proposed approach can be easily extended and re-trained for the classification of chest X-ray images with various pathologies. The next chapter considered not only classification problem but localization in a more larger dataset with several pathologies in order to consider the explainability of the developed models.

Chapter 7

CLN: A multi-task deep neural network for chest X-ray image localisation and classification

This research further went on expand from the previous chapter by solving a localization problem. Despite the fact that deep learning methods have recently achieved impressive performance in CXR image classification, but physicians are reluctant to adopt and trust such systems due to their lack of interpretability. A potential solution to this problem lies in the localisation of detected pathologies within CXR images. CXR classification and localisation are two interconnected tasks. CXR classification aims to classify a given CXR image into different predefined classes, typically referring to specific pathologies, whereas localisation focuses on identifying the regions of interest (ROIs) within the CXR image that refer to specific abnormalities. Accurate localisation can help in establishing trust to a DL model as it can enhance its interpretability, thus potentially enabling its use in clinical practice. Zhou et al. [308] introduced the concept of Class Activation Mapping (CAM) for localising ROIs in an image. CAM provides a way to generate heat-maps that highlight the discriminative regions contributing to the classification decision, providing insights into the ROIs for abnormality detection. By applying a thresholding technique to separate ROIs, the localised regions are extracted, providing a visual explanation of the areas that significantly contribute to the target class predicted by a CNN model [85, 233].

7.1 Research Methodology

This research proposed the *CXR Localisation Network (CLN)*, a multi-task deep neural network for the task of CXR image localisation and classification. The proposed architecture relies on a backbone that is fine-tuned for CXR image classification on a large CXR dataset that contains images with 14 pathologies. The network is then divided into two branches, one designed to classify the input CXR image into one of the available pathology classes, and one designed for the task of localisation by performing regression in order to estimate the coordinates of the bounding box that denotes the region of the CXR that contains the signs of the detected pathology. An overview of the proposed architecture is provided in Figure 7.1. The proposed architecture was trained to support the following 8 pathologies: Atelectasis, Cardiomegaly, Effusion, Infiltration, Mass, Nodule, Pneumonia, and Pneumothorax.

7.1.1 CXR data set

To develop and evaluate the proposed architecture, this research used the NIH's ChestX-ray14 CXR data set [280]. The data set contains 112,120 CXR images of 30,805 subjects. Images are in png format with a resolution of 1024×1024 , and are associated with one or more of 14 different pathologies, i.e. atelectasis, cardiomegaly, effusion, infiltration, mass, nodule, pneumonia, pneumothorax, consolidation, edema, emphysema, fibrosis, pleural thickening, and hernia. Furthermore, the data set contains 984 bounding box coordinates for 880

FIGURE 7.1: An overview of the proposed method. CE: Cross-entropy, IoU: Intersection over the Union, FC: Fully-connected.

of the CXR images that were hand-annotated by board-certified radiologists for 8 pathology classes: atelectasis, cardiomegaly, effusion, infiltration, mass, nodule, pneumonia, and pneumothorax. In this work, the data set was utilised in two different manners.

This research first separated the 880 bounding box annotated CXR images from the full dataset. The remaining images which were not annotated was used for fine-tuning the feature extraction backbone of the proposed architecture. The second stage was to use the subset of 880 bounding box annotated CXR images for training and evaluating the final multi-task network after performing a random stratified splitting into a training (80%) and test (20%) set. The initial training set was further divided into a training (90%) and a validation (10%) set. Furthermore, all images were resized to 224×224 pixels. It must be noted that the annotated CXR images are not included in the training and validation sets of the feature extraction backbone of the proposed architecture, thus there is no danger of data leakage and overfitting.

7.1.2 Image feature extraction backbone

During the first stage of the proposed multi-task neural network architecture, the input CXR image is passed through a feature extraction module in order to compute an appropriate representation of the image. This feature extraction module constitutes the backbone of the proposed architecture and relies on a convolutional neural network (CNN) that has been pre-trained on the task of image classification. For our network’s backbone, this research opted to use pre-trained models trained on the extensive ImageNet [142] data set. This data set consists of 1.4 million annotated images belonging to 1,000 different classes, and these models have demonstrated exceptional efficiency in extracting image features, as evidenced by their outstanding classification performance in various applications. The models examined in this work as the backbone of the proposed architecture where CheXnet (i.e. a DenseNet121) [210], EfficientB4 [259], InceptionV3 [257], and Resnet50v2 [100].

The pre-trained feature extraction backbone was fine-tuned on CXR images by training it using the full NIH CXR data set that contained 14 pathologies. To this end, as shown in Figure 7.1, a flatten layer was added after the convolutional base of the backbone network, followed by a fully connected layer of size 14, and using a sigmoid activation function for the final classification.

Given the small number of annotated CXR images in the data set compared to the total number (880 vs. 112,120), as well as the smaller number of pathologies (8 vs. 14), this research opted to fine-tune the feature extraction backbone on the full NIH data set in order to create a more efficient and generalisable CXR image feature extractor by exploiting the significantly large number of images in the full data set. Furthermore, it must be noted that

the annotated images were not included in the training and validation sets of the full data set.

As illustrated in Figure 7.1, the convolutional base of the fine-tuned model was then used as the first stage of the proposed multi-task neural network architecture, followed by a flattening layer. After the flattening layer, the network is subsequently split into two parallel branches, one targeting CXR image classification, and one targeting CXR image localisation. Considering that various CNNs can be used as the image feature extraction backbone of the proposed CLN architecture, this research utilised the following naming convention for clarity: CLN-BackboneCNN. For example, CLN-ResNet50V2 refers to our proposed CLN architecture using a ResNet50V2 model as its image feature extraction backbone.

7.1.3 CXR image classification module

For the CXR image classification module of the proposed architecture, the output of the flattening layer after the feature extraction backbone is passed to a fully-connected layer of size 8 that uses a SoftMax activation function for the final classification into the 8 pathologies included in the annotated subset of the NIH data set, i.e. atelectasis, cardiomegaly, effusion, infiltration, mass, nodule, pneumonia, and pneumothorax. Since the loss function that will be used for training will take into consideration both classification and localisation performance, the network can only be trained with CXR images for which localisation annotations exist. Consequently, out of the 14 pathologies included in the NIH dataset, only the 8 include in the annotated subset can be supported by the CXR image classification module.

7.1.4 CXR image localisation module

For the CXR image localisation module of the proposed architecture, the output of the flattening layer after the feature extraction backbone is passed through a series of four fully-connected layers. The first, second, and third fully-connected layers have a size of 512, 256, and 128, respectively, and they all use a ReLU activation function. The final fully-connected layer has a size of 4 and also uses a ReLU activation function in order to ensure that the output values cannot be negative. The four outputs of the final fully-connected layer correspond to the values x_1, x_2, y_1, y_2 of a bounding box defined by the coordinates $(x_1, y_1), (x_1, y_2), (x_2, y_1), (x_2, y_2)$. The CXR image localisation branch in our proposed architecture utilises the CXR image features extracted by the feature extraction backbone module. Its purpose is to estimate the region (bounding box) within the CXR image that corresponds to the pathology prediction made by the CXR image classification branch, employing regression techniques.

7.1.5 Loss function & Training

To train the proposed architecture, this research proposed the use of a loss function that combines two loss metrics, one for classification and one for localisation, with their combination controlled by a hyperparameter λ that defines the contribution of each loss to the total loss. For the classification metric, the Cross-Entropy loss (L_{CE}) was selected, as is commonly done across the literature. For the localisation metric, this research selected the *Intersection over Union* (IoU) metric, which describes the extend of overlap between the predicted bounding box and the ground-truth bounding box, with higher overlap leading to higher IoU values. IoU is defined as

$$IoU(B_{pred}, B_{gt}) = \frac{|B_{pred} \cap B_{gt}|}{|B_{pred} \cup B_{gt}|}, \quad (7.1)$$

where B_{pred} is the predicted bounding box and B_{gt} is the ground-truth bounding box. IoU ranges between 0 and 1, with 0 denoting no overlap and 1 denoting perfect overlap. Higher overlap corresponds to better localisation and leads to higher IoU values, thus we define the IoU loss as:

$$L_{IoU} = 1 - IoU(B_{pred}, B_{gt}) \quad (7.2)$$

The final loss function for the training of the proposed architecture is then defined as:

$$L_{total} = \lambda L_{CE} + (1 - \lambda)L_{IoU} \quad (7.3)$$

The contribution of the classification loss (L_{CE}) to the total loss (L_{total}) is controlled by the hyperparameter λ , while the contribution of the localisation loss (L_{IoU}) is controlled by $(1 - \lambda)$. By combining these two losses, the overall loss function aims to capture both classification and localisation errors, with the trade-off between the two losses controlled by the hyperparameter λ . Furthermore, given that both L_{CE} and L_{IoU} take values within the range $[0, 1]$, L_{total} also takes values within $[0, 1]$.

The proposed multi-task neural network architecture was trained using the proposed loss function and the Adam [138] optimiser with a batch size of 16 and an initial learning rate of 0.001 that was reduced by a factor of 2 after every 4 epochs, with a lower limit of 0.000001. Early stopping was also applied, with training stopping after 20 epochs with no improvement in validation loss.

7.2 Experimental Results

7.2.1 Evaluation Protocol & Metrics

The proposed multi-task neural network architecture for CXR image localisation and classification underwent training and evaluation using the subset of 880 annotated CXR images, encompassing 8 different pathologies. The performance of the network was then compared against state-of-the-art methods. Four variants of the proposed CLN architecture were evaluated, CLN-ResNet0V2, CLN-EfficientNetB4, CLN-InceptionV3, and CLN-CheXNet, each differing in terms of the image feature extraction backbone used. To ensure a fair performance evaluation, localisation and classification performance was evaluated according to the performance metrics utilised in the compared works. To this end, classification performance was evaluated in terms of the area under the ROC curve (AUC), whereas localisation performance was evaluated using the IoU metric, computed using the predicted and the ground truth bounding boxes. As is common across the literature [99, 151, 190, 280], IoU accuracy is defined by considering the localisation to be correct when the computed IoU is larger than a fixed IoU threshold $T(IoU)$. Consequently, the reported localisation accuracy for a given threshold $T(IoU)$ denotes the percentage of images for which the IoU between the predicted and the ground truth bounding box was higher than the threshold $T(IoU)$. The proposed CLN architecture was evaluated for seven different IoU thresholds, i.e. $T(IoU) \in \{0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7\}$.

7.2.2 Pathology Localisation

The four variants of the proposed CLN architecture were evaluated in terms of IoU accuracy against five state-of-the-art CXR image localisation methods, i.e. ViT [99], Wang et al. [280], RGT [99], Li et al. [151], and Ouyang et al. [190]. Localisation results are summarised in Table 7.1 for each of the 8 pathologies included in the annotated subset of the NIH data set. The mean IoU accuracy across all pathologies is also reported for all the examined methods and is also illustrated in Figure 7.2. From Table 7.1 and Figure 7.2, it is evident that all the four examined variants of the proposed CLN architecture outperform the compared state-of-the-art localisation methods for all the examined IoU thresholds, achieving a maximum mean IoU accuracy of 0.855 for $T(IoU) = 0.1$ using the CLN-CheXNet variant. In comparison, the best state-of-the-art method (Ouyang et al. [190]) achieved a mean IoU accuracy of 0.820 for the same threshold. At $T(IoU) = 0.1$, the variants of the proposed architecture achieved an improvement in the localisation performance of individual pathologies for 6 out of the 8 pathologies, performing worse only for effusion, for which [190] achieved an IoU accuracy of 0.89 compared to 0.83 for the proposed method. For cardiomegaly, both the proposed method and [190] achieved perfect localisation performance, with IoU accuracy reaching 1.0.

The improvement in localisation performance of the proposed method compared to the state of the art becomes more substantial for higher IoU thresholds, as shown in Figure 7.2

FIGURE 7.2: Pathology localisation results for the examined IoU thresholds.

and Table 7.1. At $T(IoU) = 0.2$, the highest mean IoU accuracy is improved by 14.7% compared to [190] (0.826 vs. 0.720), achieving an improvement for 7 out of the 8 pathologies, whereas both [190] and the proposed CLN method achieved a perfect localisation performance for cardiomegaly. At $T(IoU) = 0.3$, the improvement is 33.3% (0.800 for CLN-EfficientNetB4 vs. 0.600 for [190]), outperforming the other methods for all pathologies apart from cardiomegaly (0.97 vs. 1.00 for [190]). At $T(IoU) = 0.4$ the improvement is 63.7% (0.753 vs. 0.460), performing considerably better for all pathologies besides cardiomegaly (0.97 vs. 1.00 for [190]). The improvement at $T(IoU) = 0.5$ and $T(IoU) = 0.6$ rises to 118.2% (0.720 vs. 0.330) and 160.8% (0.626 vs. 0.240), respectively, achieving better localisation for all pathologies excluding cardiomegaly (0.97 vs. 0.99 and 0.90 vs. 0.97, respectively). Finally, the proposed CLN method achieved a remarkable improvement of 246.7% (0.520 vs. 0.150) over the state of the art for $T(IoU) = 0.7$, achieving better localisation for all the examined pathologies.

It must be noted that for the reported results, CLN-ResNet50V2 and CLN-EfficientNetB4 were trained with $\lambda = 0.1$, whereas CLN-InceptionV3 and CLN-CheXNet were trained with $\lambda = 0.4$. Models were trained and fine-tuned using the training and validation subsets of the bounding box annotated CXR images from the NIH data set, and results are reported for the test subset. Examples of the predicted bounding boxes for each pathology are shown in Figure 7.3.

7.2.3 Pathology Classification

This research evaluated the performance of the proposed method for pathology classification of the 8 pathologies in the annotated subset of the NIH data set by comparing to state-of-the-art methods for CXR image classification. In the experimental comparison, this research included the five CXR localisation methods examined in the previous section, as well as seven additional CXR image classification methods (CrossViT [99], PS-ViT [99], DNet-Loc [95], CAN [165], Liu et al. [156], Han et al. [98], Rajpurkar et al. [210]). Classification performance was reported in Table 7.2 in terms of the AUC score for each individual pathology, as well in terms of the mean AUC across the eight pathologies. From this table, it is evident that the CLN-ResNet50V2 variant of the proposed architecture outperformed all the compared methods in terms of mean AUC, achieving a mean AUC of 0.893. The second best mean AUC (0.849) was achieved by the proposed CLN-CheXNet, whereas the third best (0.839) by RGT [99]. From Table 7.2, it is evident that, compared to the state of the art, the variants of the proposed architecture were able to achieve improved AUC for 6 out of the 8 pathologies (cardiomegaly, infiltration, mass, nodule, pneumonia, pneumothorax). For atelectasis, the best AUC (0.83) was achieved by both variants of the proposed architecture and

TABLE 7.1: Pathology localisation results using state-of-the-art methods and the proposed method for four different backbone models on the NIH chest X-ray dataset. Results are measured by IoU accuracy at a fixed threshold ([0.1,0.7]).

T(IoU)	Method	Atelectasis	Cardiomegaly	Effusion	Infiltration	Mass	Nodule	Pneumonia	Pneumothorax	Mean
0.1	ViT [99]	0.58	0.91	0.61	0.77	0.44	0.11	0.75	0.25	0.553
	Wang et al. [280]	0.69	0.94	0.66	0.71	0.40	0.14	0.63	0.38	0.569
	RGT [99]	0.61	0.95	0.65	0.82	0.50	0.13	0.79	0.28	0.591
	Li et al. [151]	0.71	0.98	0.87	0.92	0.71	0.40	0.60	0.63	0.728
	Ouyang et al. [190]	0.71	1.00	0.89	0.88	0.76	0.65	0.91	0.78	0.820
	CLN-ResNet50V2 (ours)	0.76	0.93	0.73	0.92	0.65	0.94	0.92	0.72	0.822
	CLN-EfficientNetB4 (ours)	0.84	0.97	0.73	1.00	0.56	0.94	0.92	0.79	0.844
	CLN-InceptionV3 (ours)	0.89	1.00	0.75	0.86	1.00	0.77	0.91	0.62	0.850
	CLN-CheXNet (ours)	0.79	1.00	0.83	0.84	0.88	0.75	1.00	0.75	0.855
0.2	ViT [99]	0.38	0.85	0.39	0.55	0.24	0.01	0.51	0.15	0.385
	Wang et al. [280]	0.47	0.68	0.45	0.48	0.26	0.05	0.35	0.23	0.371
	RGT [99]	0.41	0.91	0.41	0.59	0.26	0.05	0.57	0.19	0.424
	Li et al. [151]	0.53	0.97	0.76	0.83	0.59	0.29	0.50	0.51	0.623
	Ouyang et al. [190]	0.54	1.00	0.75	0.79	0.67	0.53	0.86	0.60	0.720
	CLN-ResNet50V2 (ours)	0.68	0.93	0.63	0.92	0.65	0.94	0.89	0.72	0.794
	CLN-EfficientNetB4 (ours)	0.81	0.97	0.73	1.00	0.56	0.88	0.92	0.74	0.826
	CLN-InceptionV3 (ours)	0.78	1.00	0.68	0.82	1.00	0.77	0.77	0.62	0.805
	CLN-CheXNet (ours)	0.79	0.97	0.80	0.84	0.82	0.69	1.00	0.70	0.826
0.3	ViT [99]	0.20	0.45	0.19	0.32	0.06	0.00	0.21	0.02	0.181
	Wang et al. [280]	0.24	0.46	0.30	0.28	0.15	0.04	0.17	0.13	0.221
	RGT [99]	0.28	0.79	0.22	0.38	0.12	0.01	0.41	0.05	0.283
	Li et al. [151]	0.36	0.94	0.56	0.66	0.45	0.17	0.39	0.44	0.496
	Ouyang et al. [190]	0.40	1.00	0.52	0.68	0.58	0.46	0.69	0.43	0.600
	CLN-ResNet50V2 (ours)	0.60	0.82	0.57	0.92	0.65	0.88	0.89	0.72	0.755
	CLN-EfficientNetB4 (ours)	0.76	0.97	0.73	1.00	0.56	0.88	0.77	0.74	0.800
	CLN-InceptionV3 (ours)	0.78	0.97	0.68	0.82	0.95	0.65	0.77	0.57	0.773
	CLN-CheXNet (ours)	0.70	0.97	0.77	0.80	0.77	0.69	1.00	0.65	0.792
0.4	ViT [99]	0.10	0.21	0.03	0.05	0.02	0.00	0.04	0.00	0.056
	Wang et al. [280]	0.09	0.28	0.20	0.12	0.07	0.01	0.08	0.07	0.115
	RGT [99]	0.17	0.54	0.13	0.18	0.07	0.01	0.26	0.02	0.173
	Li et al. [151]	0.25	0.88	0.37	0.50	0.33	0.11	0.26	0.29	0.374
	Ouyang et al. [190]	0.26	1.00	0.29	0.56	0.40	0.35	0.50	0.32	0.460
	CLN-ResNet50V2 (ours)	0.61	0.82	0.50	0.92	0.65	0.75	0.89	0.72	0.731
	CLN-EfficientNetB4 (ours)	0.76	0.97	0.60	0.91	0.56	0.63	0.73	0.68	0.730
	CLN-InceptionV3 (ours)	0.78	0.90	0.54	0.77	0.90	0.59	0.77	0.48	0.716
	CLN-CheXNet (ours)	0.70	0.97	0.67	0.76	0.71	0.63	1.00	0.60	0.753
0.5	ViT [99]	0.05	0.15	0.01	0.04	0.02	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.034
	Wang et al. [280]	0.05	0.18	0.11	0.07	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.03	0.061
	RGT [99]	0.08	0.32	0.05	0.09	0.05	0.00	0.12	0.01	0.090
	Li et al. [151]	0.14	0.84	0.22	0.30	0.22	0.07	0.17	0.19	0.269
	Ouyang et al. [190]	0.15	0.99	0.14	0.33	0.27	0.22	0.35	0.22	0.330
	CLN-ResNet50V2 (ours)	0.58	0.74	0.50	0.92	0.59	0.69	0.89	0.72	0.703
	CLN-EfficientNetB4 (ours)	0.70	0.97	0.47	0.82	0.50	0.50	0.73	0.68	0.671
	CLN-InceptionV3 (ours)	0.76	0.84	0.39	0.77	0.90	0.41	0.77	0.48	0.665
	CLN-CheXNet (ours)	0.70	0.91	0.60	0.72	0.71	0.63	0.96	0.55	0.720
0.6	ViT [99]	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.010
	Wang et al. [280]	0.02	0.08	0.05	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.029
	RGT [99]	0.02	0.15	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.00	0.06	0.00	0.041
	Li et al. [151]	0.07	0.73	0.15	0.18	0.16	0.03	0.10	0.12	0.193
	Ouyang et al. [190]	0.08	0.97	0.05	0.18	0.14	0.15	0.27	0.11	0.240
	CLN-ResNet50V2 (ours)	0.58	0.74	0.47	0.88	0.53	0.31	0.89	0.61	0.626
	CLN-EfficientNetB4 (ours)	0.60	0.90	0.33	0.77	0.25	0.44	0.73	0.53	0.569
	CLN-InceptionV3 (ours)	0.65	0.84	0.29	0.64	0.79	0.35	0.68	0.43	0.583
	CLN-CheXNet (ours)	0.52	0.81	0.50	0.72	0.53	0.31	0.92	0.40	0.588
0.7	ViT [99]	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.001
	Wang et al. [280]	0.01	0.03	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.011
	RGT [99]	0.01	0.04	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.015
	Li et al. [151]	0.04	0.52	0.07	0.09	0.11	0.01	0.05	0.05	0.118
	Ouyang et al. [190]	0.02	0.77	0.01	0.12	0.08	0.10	0.06	0.03	0.150
	CLN-ResNet50V2 (ours)	0.47	0.74	0.43	0.80	0.29	0.13	0.85	0.44	0.520
	CLN-EfficientNetB4 (ours)	0.46	0.77	0.17	0.73	0.19	0.19	0.69	0.26	0.432
	CLN-InceptionV3 (ours)	0.35	0.84	0.25	0.64	0.42	0.24	0.64	0.33	0.463
	CLN-CheXNet (ours)	0.33	0.81	0.43	0.60	0.24	0.13	0.71	0.35	0.450

*A set to 0.1 for CLN-ResNet50V2 and CLN-EfficientNetB4, and to 0.4 for CLN-InceptionV3 and CLN-CheXNet.

TABLE 7.2: AUC scores for the annotated subset of the NIH dataset for the task of CXR image classification. Results ordered by ascending mean AUC. Methods in bold are also included in the localisation performance comparison.

Method	Atelectasis	Cardiomegaly	Effusion	Infiltration	Mass	Nodule	Pneumonia	Pneumothorax	Mean
Wang et al. [280]	0.72	0.81	0.78	0.61	0.71	0.67	0.63	0.81	0.718
ViT [99]	0.74	0.78	0.81	0.72	0.70	0.66	0.65	0.76	0.728
CrossViT [99]	0.69	0.71	0.72	0.72	0.74	0.79	0.82	0.88	0.759
PS-ViT [99]	0.75	0.81	0.82	0.73	0.79	0.73	0.69	0.81	0.766
DNetLoc [95]	0.77	0.88	0.83	0.71	0.82	0.76	0.73	0.85	0.794
CAN [165]	0.78	0.89	0.83	0.70	0.84	0.77	0.72	0.86	0.799
Li et al. [151] ^a	0.80	0.87	0.87	0.70	0.83	0.77	0.67	0.88	0.799
Ouyang et al. [190]	0.77	0.87	0.83	0.71	0.83	0.79	0.72	0.88	0.800
Liu et al. [156]	0.79	0.87	0.88	0.69	0.81	0.73	0.75	0.89	0.801
Seyyed-Kalantari et al. [237]	0.81	0.92	0.87	0.72	0.83	0.78	0.76	0.88	0.821
CLN-InceptionV3 (ours)	0.83	0.96	0.70	0.71	0.86	0.92	0.78	0.84	0.825
Han et al. [98]	0.83	0.92	0.87	0.76	0.85	0.76	0.77	0.86	0.828
Rajpurkar et al. [210]	0.82	0.91	0.88	0.72	0.86	0.78	0.76	0.89	0.828
CLN-EfficientNetB4 (ours)	0.77	0.94	0.79	0.83	0.73	0.94	0.77	0.87	0.831
RGT [99]	0.80	0.92	0.78	0.86	0.88	0.88	0.79	0.81	0.839
CLN-CheXNet (ours)	0.75	0.96	0.84	0.74	0.90	0.86	0.78	0.97	0.849
CLN-ResNet50V2 (ours)	0.83	0.90	0.81	0.92	0.90	0.95	0.91	0.92	0.893

^aResults refer to the 80% annotated - 80% unannotated setting

^aA set to 0.1 for CLN-ResNet50V2 and CLN-EfficientNetB4, and to 0.4 for CLN-InceptionV3 and CLN-CheXNet.

FIGURE 7.3: Visualisation of pathology localisation for a randomly selected CXR image for each pathology. Green and red denote the ground-truth and the predicted bounding box, respectively, using the proposed CLN-CheXNet model.

the Han et al. [98] method, whereas for effusion, the best AUC of 0.88 was achieved by the Liu et al. [156] and the Rajpurkar et al. [210] methods, with the proposed method achieving a maximum AUC of 0.84.

7.2.4 Ablation study

It is evident from the experimental results that the performance of the proposed CLN architecture can be affected by the model used as the image feature extraction backbone, by the value of the hyperparameter λ , and by the IoU threshold used to compute the IoU accuracy. This research evaluated the effect of these hyperparameters by conducting various ablation experiments.

The effect of the IoU threshold on the mean IoU accuracy is examined in Figure 7.2. There is a clear negative relation between $T(IoU)$ and mean IoU accuracy for all the examined methods, with higher $T(IoU)$ leading to lower mean IoU accuracy in all cases. Nevertheless, it is evident that the proposed CLN architecture is more resistant to the increase in

FIGURE 7.4: Pathology localisation and classification results for the four examined variants of the proposed model in relation to the λ hyperparameter. Values in the y axis depict mean IoU accuracy for the $T(IoU)$ series, and AUC score for the AUC series.

$T(IoU)$, exhibiting much slower decay in mean IoU accuracy compared to the state-of-the-art methods, which demonstrated rapid decay as $T(IoU)$ increased.

The effect of the λ hyperparameter on the classification mean AUC score and on the localisation mean IoU accuracy is examined in Figure 7.4 for $\lambda \in [0.1, 0.9]$. Given the proposed loss function (Eq. 7.3), a higher λ implies a higher weight to the cross-entropy loss and a lower weight to the IoU loss, i.e. a higher weight for the classification metric and lower for the localisation metric. A $\lambda = 0$ or $\lambda = 1$ would lead to only the classification or the localisation metric to be considered, respectively. λ 's effect on mean AUC score seems to depend on the model used as the image feature extraction backbone. Mean AUC scores for CLN-InceptionV3 and CLN-CheXNet are less affected by λ , with scores ranging from 0.773 to 0.837 ($\sigma = 0.022$) and from 0.818 to 0.887 ($\sigma = 0.021$), respectively, whereas CLN-EfficientNetB4 and CLN-ResNet50V2 are much more affected, with scores ranging from 0.713 to 0.831 ($\sigma = 0.033$) and from 0.711 to 0.893 ($\sigma = 0.066$), respectively.

From Figure 7.4, it is evident that λ 's effect on mean IoU accuracy is much more dramatic compared to AUC. λ values at the mid of its range seem to underperform considerably. Localisation performance seems to drop as λ increases and then improves again for higher values. The observed trend for each variant is consistent across the different IoU thresholds ($T(IoU)$), but the drop in localisation performance for mid-valued λ is less prominent for $T(IoU) = 0.1$. For CLN-EfficientNetB4 and CLN-ResNet50V2, low λ led to higher mean IoU accuracy for higher $T(IoU)$ values, whereas for CLN-InceptionV3 and CLN-CheXNet, a $\lambda = 0.4$ provided the best localisation performance for $T(IoU) > 0.1$. For $T(IoU) = 0.1$, higher λ values led to better localisation performance in most cases.

Considering that the proposed architecture aims at both pathology classification and localisation, the selected λ should maximise both mean AUC and mean IoU accuracy. However, as shown in Figure 7.4, the best mean AUC is typically achieved for a different λ than the one providing the best mean IoU accuracy, thus a trade-off must be made during hyperparameter tuning. In this work, we attempted to achieve a balance between the two metrics, leading to $\lambda = 0.1$ being selected for CLN-ResNet50V2 and CLN-EfficientNetB4, and $\lambda = 0.4$ for CLN-InceptionV3 and CLN-CheXNet.

7.2.5 Further Discussion

It is evident from Table 7.1 and Table 7.2 that the proposed CLN architecture outperforms the examined state-of-the-art models for both CXR image localisation and classification. Among the four examined CLN variants, CLN-CheXNet achieved the best balance among localisation and classification, ranking first among all models for localisation and second behind CLN-ResNet50V2 for classification. Apart from the improved performance, the proposed approach offers two significant advantages over the compared methods; better stability in localisation performance as the IoU threshold increases, and relative simplicity that leads to lower computational complexity. As shown in Figure 7.2, mean IoU accuracy for the examined state-of-the-art localisation methods drops sharply with the increase in $T(IoU)$, whereas the accuracy for the variants of the proposed architecture drops at a much slower rate. Regarding its complexity, the proposed architecture relies on a pre-trained CNN model

and fully-connected layers for classification and for localisation via regression. The compared state-of-the-art approaches employ combinations of transformers, attention mechanisms, and complex network structures, leading to a substantial increase in complexity.

However, the proposed architecture has some limitations. Its training requires CXR images annotated with bounding boxes from expert radiologists. Annotating large numbers of CXR images is an arduous, time-consuming, and costly task, leading to limited availability of such annotated images for many pathologies. In addition, the proposed architecture does not support the prediction of multiple bounding boxes on the CXR image, thus being limited in providing localisation for a single pathology. Finally, a trade-off between classification and localisation performance must be made during hyperparameter tuning, as the ablation study showed that the best performance is achieved for different λ for each task.

7.3 Summary

This research proposed the Chest X-ray Localisation Network (CLN), a multi-task deep neural network for the task of CXR image classification and localisation. The proposed architecture employs a pre-trained convolutional neural network as its feature extraction backbone, followed by two network branches, one tasked with CXR image classification and one tasked with CXR image localisation by predicting bounding boxes via regression. Experiments on an annotated CXR image data set that contained 8 different pathologies demonstrated that the proposed architecture was able to outperform state-of-the-art methods for both localisation and classification, achieving a maximum classification mean AUC score of 0.893 and a maximum localisation mean IoU accuracy of 0.855. The proposed architecture offers some significant advantages over the state of the art, such as better performance, slower localisation performance decay with the increase of the IoU threshold, and relative simplicity compared to the other methods. The achieved results indicate that CLN can offer an efficient solution for computer-aided CXR image diagnosis. Future work will focus on expanding the number of pathologies supported by our model, on the localisation of multiple pathologies in a single CXR image, and on supporting multiple bounding boxes in a single image.

Chapter 8

Conclusions & Future Work

8.1 Conclusions

This thesis proposed effective Machine learning systems FOR medical image analysis. The developed deep learning models are based on extracting features from images and also making use of meta-data for classification, detection and localization. The developed and implemented models were thoroughly evaluated in terms of performance, scalability, memory consumption and also compared with state of the art. The extensive research done on Machine learning applications to medical image analysis is presented in Chapter 2 as it reviews the the research done in machine learning applications to medical image analysis. Chapters 3 and 4 described evaluated several established CNN models and made adjustments on the neural networks to specifically solve classification tasks, Chapter 5 improved on previous chapters by presenting a completely new novel architecture on Vision Transformers to handle more datasets in solving classification problem. Chapter 6 proposed advanced technique for not only classification but also localization.

In Chapters 3, this research proposed a multi-modal approach for the classification of lung ultrasound images for the task of distinguishing them between “COVID-19”, “Normal”, “Pneumonia”, and “Other (lung diseases/conditions)”. The proposed approach relies on the fusion of image-based CNN features with information regarding the type of ultrasound probe (linear or convex) used to acquire the input image. Experimental results on a large lung ultrasound image dataset containing 22,776 lung ultrasound images demonstrated the superiority of the proposed approach compared to solely using the base CNN model for the classification of the images.

In Chapters 4, this research evaluated the performance of eleven deep convolutional neural network architectures for the task of classifying chest X-ray images as belonging to healthy individuals, individuals with COVID-19, or individuals with viral pneumonia. The eleven examined CNN models were selected due to their proven efficiency in image classification tasks and were modified in order to be adjusted for the task at hand. Supervised classification experiments using a 5-fold cross validation procedure was performed in order to evaluate the performance of three different modifications of the examined base CNN models on a data set with real chest X-ray images that contained normal images, COVID-19-positive images and viral pneumonia images.

In Chapters 5, this research evaluated the performance of the state-of-the-art Vision Transformer (ViT) architecture for the task of classifying various pathological conditions in chest X-ray images, and proposed the novel IEViT architecture that outperformed the original ViT for all the variants and data sets examined. Experiments on a data set for children pneumonia, a data set for Tuberculosis, a data set for COVID-19 and viral pneumonia, as well as a data set for COVID-19, demonstrated the consistent improvement in classification performance of the proposed IEViT model’s variants over the respective original ViT model’s variants.

In Chapter 6, this research proposed the Chest X-ray Localisation Network (CLN), a multi-output deep neural network for the task of CXR image classification and localisation. The proposed architecture employs a pre-trained convolutional neural network as its feature extraction backbone, followed by two network branches, one tasked with CXR image classification and one tasked with CXR image localisation by predicting bounding boxes via regression. Experiments on an annotated CXR image data set that contained 8 different

pathologies demonstrated that the proposed architecture was able to outperform state-of-the-art methods for both localisation and classification.

8.2 Future Work

- Future work will include a replication study using a much larger data set of chest X-ray images, as well as a thorough study of the generalisation ability of the developed models by training and testing the models on diverse data sets from different sources and with X-ray images acquired by different X-ray machines.
- Examining the performance of the proposed IEViT model on multiple pathologies, on exploring ways to reduce the overall computational complexity of the model, and on examining the use of transfer learning based on X-ray images.
- Optimizing the developed models to be applied in real world clinical settings. The majority of the time, deep learning models are not trained and tested in a medical environment. Deep learning models, however, must be able to deal with a range of variables, including various medical image types, noise, abnormalities, and various patient demographics, in order to be employed in real-world scenarios.
- Multi-Modal Fusion for Enhanced Diagnosis: Although the focus of this thesis has been on individual imaging modalities, merging multiple modalities, such as integrating MRI, CT scans, and PET scans, can result to a more robust model for different types of medical image diagnosis.
- Integrating Clinical Data: A diagnostic strategy might result from combining medical imaging data with clinical records, genetics, and other patient-specific information. The development of methods that incorporate numerous data sources can improve the precision of disease prediction and treatment advice.

In conclusion, this thesis paved the way for numerous applications of machine learning in the field of medical imaging. The stated future work directions show the potential for ongoing developments that may lead to improved patient outcomes, more precise diagnosis, and personalised treatment plans. To fully realise the potential of AI-driven healthcare solutions, it will be essential to solve these difficulties as machine learning and medical imaging develop.

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